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Exploring the Modulatory Effects of Adipose-Derived Stem Cells on Fibroblasts in Chronic Radiation-Induced Fibrosis

Dr Anna Onderková

21119813

MSc Burns, Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery

Division of Surgery & Interventional Science

University College London

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Abstract

Background: Radiation-induced fibrosis (RIF) is a common and debilitating side effect of radiotherapy in head and neck cancer patients. Despite its prevalence, effective treatments are lacking. However, autologous fat grafting can not only restore volume in these patients but also help with local tissue regeneration. This has been attributed to adipose-derived stem cells (ADSCs)'s anti-inflammatory and pro-regenerative properties within the grafts. Yet, the precise cellular mechanisms underlying their effects on the chronic inflammatory response in RIF remain to be elucidated.

Methods: In this study, tissue samples were collected from patients with RIF of the head and neck. ADSCs and fibroblasts were isolated from these samples and subsequently expanded in vitro. The direct interactions between ADSCs and fibroblasts were assessed through co-culture experiments. The anti-inflammatory effects of ADSCs on fibroblasts were evaluated by measuring the expression of 9 target genes: *COL1A1*, *TGFB1*, *ACTA2*, *MMP1*, *MMP9*, *TNC*, *CCL19*, *CDKN2A*, *CDKN1A*. The impact on procollagen production, as a key component of extracellular matrix remodelling in fibrosis, was assessed using an Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay. Preliminary clinical outcomes were assessed using objective and subjective measures.

Results: Findings demonstrated that ADSCs significantly modulated the expression of *COL1A1*, a gene crucial to extracellular matrix production, aligning its expression in RIF fibroblasts closer to levels found in normal fibroblasts. The study also revealed a significant increase in procollagen production in RIF fibroblasts when exposed to ADSCs in both conditioned medium and co-culture conditions. However, no statistically significant variations were observed in the expression of genes related to fibroblast transformation, extracellular matrix degradation, remodelling, immune regulation, and cellular senescence.

Conclusion: This study provides insights into the cellular mechanisms by which ADSCs may affect the chronic inflammatory response in RIF, particularly through the modulation of extracellular matrix production. These findings suggest the potential therapeutic role of ADSCs in the treatment of RIF, highlighting the importance of further research to optimise therapeutic protocols, determine underlying molecular mechanisms, and assess long-term safety and efficacy.

Key Words

Radiation-induced Fibrosis; skin fibrosis; ADSC; adipose derived stem cells; lipotransfer; autologous fat grafting

Supervisors

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Statutory declaration

I, Dr Anna Onderkova, confirm that the work presented in this thesis is my own. Where information has been derived from other sources or with the help of others, I confirm that this has been indicated in the text.

Abbreviations

ACTA2 - alpha smooth muscle actin gene

ADSC - Adipose-Derived Stem Cell

AFG -Autologous fat grafting / AFT - Autologous Fat Transfer

CCL19 – Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 19

CDKN1A – cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1A

CDKN2A – cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1A

COL1A1 - collagen type 1 pro- α 1(I) chain gene

DMEM/F12 – Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutri Mix F12

DAMPs – damage-associated molecular patterns

ECM - Extracellular Matrix

EGF - Epidermal Groth factor

ELISA – Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

FBS – Fetal bovine serum

FGF - fibroblast growth factor

HDF - Human Dermal Fibroblast

IL - Interleukin

MMP – Matrix metalloproteinase

PBS – Phosphate buffered saline

RIF - Radiation-Induced Fibrosis

ROS – Reactive oxygen species

RT-qPCR – Quantitative reverse transcription PCR

TGFB1 - transforming growth factor beta 1

TNC – Tenascin - C

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Introduction

Radiation-induced Fibrosis

Radiotherapy, as a prevalent treatment modality for head and neck cancers, is employed either alone or as an adjuvant in over 50% of new cancer diagnoses.¹ While the acute side effects of desquamation, swelling, erythema, and pain are perhaps the most initially obvious, particularly in rapidly proliferating tissues such as epithelial surfaces and bone marrow; the chronic effects of fibrosis, late vascular damage, and atrophy secondary to ongoing inflammation can be debilitating for years to come.² Nearly any organ can develop fibrosis due to radiation exposure, but the skin is most commonly affected, with approximately 95% of patients receiving radiotherapy experiencing either immediate or delayed skin reactions.³ This can result in late side effects that significantly impact their quality of life and socioeconomic well-being.⁴

Radiation-induced fibrosis (RIF) is a prominent late side effect of radiation exposure, characterised by uncontrolled wound healing response in the skin and muscles.¹ Chronic inflammation results in fibrosis and scarring of the skin and musculature in the irradiated area up to a year after completing treatment and worsening with time, tending to present at between 1 and 5 years after radiotherapy.⁴ At the microscopic level, RIF manifests as excessive activation and differentiation of fibroblasts, excessive extracellular matrix (ECM) deposition, and dysregulation of wound healing processes at the site of radiation injury.^{1,3}

Clinical significance

For the patient, the result is a loss of skin elasticity and regional volume, consequently leading to unsightly and constricting contractures. The tissues of the head, neck, and trunk are particularly prone to fibrosis.¹ With head and neck cancers making up a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide (yearly 650,000 cases and 330,000 deaths),⁵ and with radiotherapy being the cornerstone of treatment, this is an increasingly frequently encountered problem that reaches beyond poor aesthetic outcomes, more noticeable with movement, as the tissue takes on a wooden disfiguring texture.⁶ Some of the most severe cases in the head may involve fibrosis of the lingual

muscles and trismus, limiting mouth-opening, thus interfering with speech, mastication, and oral hygiene.⁴ In the neck, the results are similarly debilitating, with dystonia⁴ and severe functional impairments, such as ‘chin-to-chest’ deformities in which patients are unable to straighten the neck. Even in milder cases in which the patient is simply unable to turn their head to the side, this can have a profound effect, as it takes away their ability to drive and thus their independence.

Lipofilling & ADSCs

One of the few available treatment options for combating the effects of chronic RIF is through autologous fat transfer (AFT, also known as autologous fat grafting, AFG, or lipofilling; see figure 1). Although fat grafting was initially conceived as a method for simply restoring lost volume or correcting contours,⁷ observation of the tissue receiving the fat revealed a potentially more significant function – the role of adipose tissue as a possible therapeutic agent.⁸ Coleman noted this in the mid-1990s, noting a progressive enhancement in skin quality above the graft, with wrinkle softening, pore reduction, and pigmentation enhancement. Furthermore, he observed that fat grafting could potentially soften and even remove depressed scars.⁷

The body of work supporting these findings has since been significantly expanded upon in a number of clinical papers (see appendix table 1)^{9–13}, and it has been shown that AFT can greatly improve skin quality and reverse radiation injury¹⁴– including fibrosis, scarring, contractures, and pain. It works on post-traumatic and post-operative scars alike, for example, helping to resolve postmastectomy pain syndromes,¹⁵ painful retracted scars after tracheostomy,¹⁶ and improve swallowing function.^{17,18} A recent study that attempted to quantify these improvements found that aesthetic improvement was observed in 77.5% of patients and functional improvement in 89.2% of patients following AFG.¹⁹ Conversely, however, this means that a subset of patients does not respond to this treatment approach, thereby underscoring the need for a more nuanced understanding of the mechanisms behind the changes.

Figure 1: Autologous fat grafting involves the transfer of fat from the abdomen to the face and neck. This process can be visualized on a microscopic level: (a) the cannula disrupts the fibrotic bands in the scarred tissue as it injects the fat graft. This contributes to immediate contour improvements and reestablishes the subcutaneous plane. Over time, (b) the proliferation of fat cells and improved vascularity, play a crucial role in the restoration of the fibrotic, scarred tissue. Several months later (c), only minimal scar tissue remains, with a notable regeneration of skin. (Created with BioRender.com & Vectornator)

The proposed key component of the adipose tissue that confers regenerative properties is the Adipose-derived stem cell (ADSC).^{14,20} ADSCs are multipotent mesenchymal stem cells found in fat tissue with self-renewal and differentiation abilities. They can transform into various cell types from mesodermic, endodermic, and ectodermic lineages and exhibit paracrine activity.²¹ When transplanted into damaged sites, ADSCs appear to interact with their surrounding microenvironment, generating new progenitors and cells.²² Precisely how they do so in chronic RIF patients remains unexplored and is the core subject of this dissertation.

Despite a full understanding of these mechanisms, over the years, the process of lipofilling has evolved over time in order to obtain the highest possible concentration of viable ADSCs while minimising contamination and damage to surrounding tissues.⁷ Coleman improved upon the technique through an emphasis on gentle liposuction to harvest the fat, followed by centrifugation at low speeds (around 3,000 RPM for 3 minutes) to separate and purify the fat cells, and then careful reinject the fat into the desired area in small quantities to optimise blood supply and enhance graft survival.^{7,12} Today, various methods (see Figure 2), either alone or in combination, are used to process fat grafts for AFT.^{23,24} Importantly, contaminants like cellular debris, free oil, and nonviable lipoaspirate components must be removed, including blood cells, as these can cause harmful inflammation at the graft site and hasten the breakdown of the transplanted fat.⁷

Figure 2: Autologous fat grafting (AFG) is a versatile technique in reconstructive and cosmetic surgery. Various graft processing techniques exist for intraoperative use but great variability persists, resulting in unreliable clinical outcomes, with no consensus on the optimal methodology (original illustration created in Vectornator).

In general, ADSCs are hypothesised to influence cells via cell-to-cell interactions, as well as by secreting exosomes containing growth factors, cytokines, chemokines, and micro-RNA, which are crucial for angiogenesis, immunomodulation, and cell proliferation/differentiation to repair damaged tissue.^{25–28}

In particular, the anti-inflammatory and anti-fibrotic properties of ADSCs have been evidenced in multiple studies on acute radiation injury (see appendix table 2)^{1,2,29–33}. This has previously been examined in co-culture experiments like those by Saijo et al.³¹ and Yu et al.³² that investigated the effects of ADSCs and their derivatives on lymphangiogenesis and ECM-receptor interaction, respectively. Saijo et al showed that ADSCs reversed radiation-induced suppression of Human Dermal Lymphatic Endothelial Cells proliferation, potentially through lymphangiogenic factor upregulation (bFGF in particular);³¹ while Yu et al. showed that fibroblast proteomic profiles were changed by the presence of ADSCs and DMTF1, MFAP5, PI16, MMP-1 and collagen chains were amongst the proteins that were upregulated.³² Similarly, other in vitro studies like that Yao et al looking at apoptosis regulation demonstrated that culture supernatant derived from ADSCs significantly reduced radiation-induced apoptosis, emphasizing the potential of ADSCs in protecting cells from radiation-induced damage.³³

Furthermore, studies like those by Haubner et al.²⁹ and Ejaz et al.³⁴ found that ADSCs could mitigate radiation-induced endothelial cell dysfunction and downregulate fibrosis-associated genes, respectively. Additionally, ADSCs have been shown to promote cell migration and repair following radiation exposure. Shukla et al.³⁵ highlighted the ability of ADSCs to reverse dysregulated fibroblast migration, while Haubner et al.³⁶ and Xiao et al.³⁰ reported that ADSCs stimulated neovascularization, fibroblast migration, and repair of irradiated fibroblasts.

ADSCs' unique immunomodulatory properties, coupled with the fact that they do not express MHC class II nor costimulatory molecules and are thus nonimmunogenic makes them ideal for potential use in therapeutic investigations in allogeneic settings.³⁷ They have the potential to play a vital role in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine and could offer a promising and accessible source of stem cells for innovative treatments.^{22,28}

However, the major caveat in all of these studies, both in vitro and the multiple in vivo animal studies on the topic (see appendix tables 2 & 3 for comparison of durations, methodologies and

findings).^{1,20,29–32,34,36} is that the majority of these studies have focused on acute RIF, which occurs within weeks to months after radiation exposure and is characterized by inflammation, tissue damage, and oedema. Chronic RIF, on the other hand, develops months to years post-radiation and is marked by progressive tissue fibrosis, scarring, and compromised tissue function. Due to the distinct pathophysiological mechanisms involved in acute and chronic RIF,²³ it is necessary to explore the potential therapeutic impact of ADSCs on chronic RIF specifically.

This thesis attempts to address this gap, as it concentrates on chronic RIF, which represents a challenging and long-term clinical problem that necessitates novel therapeutic approaches. To the best of the author's knowledge, no previous *in vitro* studies have specifically addressed the effects of ADSCs on chronic RIF tissue. A thorough investigation of the potential therapeutic effects of ADSCs on chronic RIF cells is vital for the development of innovative treatments aimed at improving the quality of life for patients suffering from this long-term consequence of radiotherapy.

Hypotheses behind interactions between ADSCs and chronic RIF pathology

In order to attempt to understand how ADSCs modulate chronic RIF tissue, first one must take a step back and attempt to understand fibrosis in general. The fibroblast is one of the central players in wound healing and, by extension, a key player in dysregulated types of wound healing like fibrosis.³⁸ By secreting various paracrine factors and differentiating into myofibroblasts in response to tissue injury, fibroblasts promote wound repair and scar formation. Myofibroblasts take this further and are highly specialised contractile cells that express smooth muscle actin (α -SMA) and function to synthesise collagen and other components of the provisional ECM. They help to bring the wound edges together through contractile forces and then myofibroblasts typically undergo apoptosis following the completion of scar maturation.²¹

This normal process of wound healing is transient; however, when healing is dysregulated, uncontrollable secretion of factors such as TGF- β 1, caspase 1, IL-1 β , IL-18, IL-8, stromal cell-derived factor 1, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1, focal adhesion kinase, and Toll-like receptor 4, leads to the continuous production of ECM components, particularly copious quantities of

disorganised collagen, and thus hypertrophic scarring.²¹

Figure 3: Mechanisms of Fibrosis (Illustration reproduced courtesy of Cell Signaling Technology, Inc. (www.cellsignal.com)).³⁹

Fibrosis (see figure 3), a hallmark of many chronic diseases, is characterized by the excessive deposition of ECM components, primarily collagen, in response to an insult, leading to progressive scarring and functional impairment of the affected organ.^{40,41} This aberrant wound healing response typically begins with repeated tissue damage that then progresses to self-sustaining activation loops propagating further tissue damage and inflammation. The fibrotic process is a complex interplay of various cellular and molecular mechanisms, which, although sharing common pathways, exhibit distinct characteristics in different diseases. For example, in systemic sclerosis (SSc), an autoimmune disease, fibrosis is driven by multifaceted changes secondary to environmental triggers and epigenetic modifications, on top of a genetic predisposition,⁴² resulting in a combination of vascular abnormalities, immune dysregulation, and fibroblast activation induced by transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGF- β 1), leading to the overproduction of ECM proteins, resulting in skin thickening and internal organ damage.⁴³ On the other hand, lichen sclerosis, a chronic

inflammatory dermatosis, characterised by fibrosis of the papillary dermis, is believed to also involve an interplay of genetic, hormonal, infectious, and autoimmune factors driven by an inflammatory cascade, leading to the activation of fibroblasts and the subsequent deposition of collagen.⁴⁴

In contrast to these other fibrotic diseases, chronic RIF is a late side effect of radiation therapy, where fibrosis occurs as a response to the radiation-induced injury and inflammation.²³ The molecular mechanisms of RIF are also complex (see figure 4), involving a variety of signalling pathways, including the TGF β 1/Smad, WNT, 5-HT, hedgehog, and PDGF pathways,⁴¹ as well as chronic activation by free radicals such as reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the resulting DNA damage response. These pathways lead to the activation of human dermal fibroblasts, the excessive deposition of ECM, chronic hypoxia and stiffness, resulting in tissue hardening and organ dysfunction.^{7,45}

Figure 4: Summary of some of the key pathological processes involved in radiation induced fibrosis (Created using Vectornator based upon mechanisms suggested across the literature but particularly in 20,32,41,46,47)

Naturally, it is difficult to explore all of the elements of these interactions in a single experimental design. Therefore, this thesis focuses on a number of key players:

Collagen

The fibrotic response in RIF is characterised by excessive ECM production, primarily driven by the over-expression of genes such as Collagen Type I Alpha 1 Chain (*COL1A1*).⁴⁸ The *COL1A1* gene is crucial in the pathophysiology of chronic RIF. *COL1A1* encodes the pro-alpha1 chains of type I collagen, whose triple helix comprises two alpha1 chains and one alpha2 chain. Type I collagen is the most abundant structural collagen and forms the basic structure of the ECM in various tissues, including the skin and mucosa of the head and neck.⁴⁹ Post-radiation, there is an imbalance between ECM production and degradation, with a significant increase in the former, driven by upregulated expression of ECM components such as *COL1A1*.⁵⁰ Fibroblasts, the primary collagen-producing cells, transition into myofibroblasts under the influence of profibrotic factors like transforming growth factor-beta (TGF β), further amplifying *COL1A1* expression and ECM deposition.⁵¹

ADSCs hold promise in modulating this fibrotic process. ADSCs possess anti-fibrotic properties partially attributed to their ability to secrete matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), which degrade collagen, thereby counterbalancing the excessive *COL1A1* expression.¹⁴ Additionally, they can reduce the myofibroblast population either by direct cell-to-cell contact inhibiting the fibroblast-to-myofibroblast transition or by paracrine mechanisms by regulating *COL1A1* expression and thus collagen synthesis via the TGF β /Smad signalling pathway.⁵²

Fibroblast Differentiation

The aberrant activation and differentiation of fibroblasts into myofibroblasts is a crucial aspect of the fibrotic process. The TGF β 1/Smad signaling pathway not only converts fibroblasts into matrix-synthesising myofibroblasts in response to noxious stimuli but also the subsequent excessive matrix production by these cells results in tissue stiffness, scarring, atrophy, and non-functionality. TGF β 1 specifically appears to be the main cytokine responsible for the up-regulation of proliferation of

fibroblast progenitors under radiation stress.⁵³ It modulates cellular proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, and other functions. In the context of fibrosis, it plays a predominant role as a potent inducer of ECM production and fibroblast to myofibroblast differentiation.⁵⁴

Activation of the canonical TGF β 1/Smad signaling pathway thus results in elevated *COL1A1* and Alpha-Smooth Muscle Actin 2 (*ACTA2*) gene expression, thereby increasing ECM deposition and promoting the formation of contractile myofibroblasts.⁵⁵ The prolonged presence of myofibroblasts, together with the upregulation of the expression of the *ACTA2* and thus increased production of alpha-smooth muscle actin (α -SMA), thus enhancing fibroblast contractility and contributing to chronic fibrosis and tissue stiffening.^{56,57}

The role of ADSCs in TGF β 1 regulation is multifaceted. ADSCs can attenuate the TGF β 1/Smad signaling pathway, thereby reducing the profibrotic activity of TGF β 1.⁵⁸ Additionally, ADSCs can interfere with the TGF β 1-induced fibroblast to myofibroblast transition, potentially via secreted factors such as HGF and IL-10.^{59,60}

The persistence of myofibroblasts, as signified by continued upregulated *ACTA2* expression, prevents the resolution of the fibrotic response and sustains the pathological state.⁶¹ Thus the potential modulating effect of ADSCs on *ACTA2* expression and the myofibroblast population is of significant interest. Experimental evidence suggests that ADSCs may be able to alter the metabolism of the local myofibroblast population, through molecules such as adipose-derived stem cell peptide ADSCP2, which specifically targets pyruvate carboxylase and results in notable decreases in both collagen and *ACTA2* expression.^{62,63}

Tenascin-C (TNC), an ECM glycoprotein that functions as a damage-associated molecular pattern (DAMP), could also play an essential role in these processes.⁶⁴ Normally TNC is tightly regulated and associated with tissue development, with little expression after embryogenesis except for transient re-expression during wound healing and dynamic tissue remodelling.^{65,66} Radiation exposure has been found to increase the expression of TNC, which activates endogenous toll-like receptor (TLR) 4 ligand, altering cell-matrix interactions and creating a permissive environment for fibroblast activation and migration.^{67,68} TNC also stimulates the production of pro-fibrotic cytokines like TGF β 1, thus promoting ECM accumulation and myofibroblast differentiation.⁶⁹ But this is not only the case in the acute state; it has been postulated to be a major driving force in certain fibrotic states in the heart and lungs⁷⁰, as well as in maintaining persistent organ fibrosis in

systemic sclerosis.⁶⁸ Therefore, this could similarly be the case in chronic RIF but this has not yet been examined and precisely how ADSCs may influence TNC in fibrotic conditions is unclear.

Extracellular Matrix Remodelling

In a balanced tissue microenvironment, the remodelling of the ECM is finely tuned by the interplay between matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and their endogenous inhibitors, tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases (TIMPs). MMPs are a family of zinc-dependent endopeptidases. These proteolytic enzymes are capable of degrading the ECM components, thereby contributing to tissue remodelling processes. In the context of chronic RIF, MMP-1 (interstitial collagenase) and MMP-9 (gelatinase B) are potentially particularly significant.⁷¹

MMP-1 facilitates the degradation of interstitial collagens (types I, II, and III), while MMP-9 predominantly breaks down type IV and type V collagens. In normal physiological states, a balance between the activities of MMPs and their TIMPs ensures controlled ECM turnover.⁷¹ However, radiation-induced oxidative stress and inflammation disrupt this equilibrium, leading to excessive ECM deposition and fibrosis. In the early stages of radiation injury, an acute inflammatory response is associated with increased MMP activity, contributing to tissue damage and remodelling.⁷² As the tissue shifts towards a chronic fibrotic state, there is a reduction in MMP expression and/or activity and an upregulation of TIMPs, culminating in reduced ECM degradation and sustained fibrosis.⁷³

It should be noted that matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) are an extensive family of proteolytic enzymes, with MMP-2 (gelatinase A) and MMP-3 (stromelysin-1) also holding relevance in the pathophysiology. MMP-2 is capable of degrading type IV collagen, a major component of basement membranes, and is known to be involved in angiogenesis and tissue remodelling.⁷⁴ In the context of RIF, MMP-2 is often upregulated during the early stages of tissue injury, contributing to initial tissue damage and remodelling. However, as with MMP-1 and MMP-9, MMP-2 activity tends to decrease as the tissue progresses towards a chronic fibrotic state.⁷⁵

MMP-3, on the other hand, can degrade a variety of ECM components and is capable of activating other MMPs, notably proMMP-1 and proMMP-9. Its overexpression in response to tissue injury and inflammation might exacerbate tissue damage, promoting fibrogenesis.⁷⁶

These activities of MMPs are counterbalanced by Tissue Inhibitors of Metalloproteinases (TIMPs), a group of endogenous inhibitors. The TIMP family consists of four members (TIMP-1, TIMP-2, TIMP-3, and TIMP-4), each capable of inhibiting the activity of MMPs, thus preventing excessive ECM degradation. In conditions like RIF, TIMP expression tends to be upregulated, often outpacing the expression of MMPs, leading to reduced ECM degradation and fibrosis.⁷⁷

ADSCs may offer therapeutic benefits by modulating this MMP-TIMP balance. They have been shown to secrete MMPs and can potentially upregulate MMP-1 and MMP-9 expression, promoting collagen degradation and counteracting fibrosis.⁷⁸ Moreover, ADSCs might downregulate TIMP expression, further encouraging ECM breakdown and limiting fibrosis.^{79,80} Further understanding of this regulatory mechanism may offer novel insights into the therapeutic potential of ADSCs in managing RIF.

Immune Regulation

Immune dysregulation also plays a pivotal role in the progression and perpetuation of RIF. The complex interplay of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory factors, the activation and recruitment of various immune cells, and the dysregulation of chemokines and cytokines all contribute to a sustained immune response, ultimately leading to fibrogenesis. Although multiple immune-related factors are involved in this intricate network, cytokines such as C-C Motif Chemokine Ligand 19 (CCL19) are of interest because they tell us about ongoing vascular inflammation in fibrotic tissue. Studies have suggested that vascular injury, resulting in inflammation, contributing to lymphocyte homing and activation, is a key pathogenic mechanism in systemic sclerosis⁸¹ Sustained inflammation promotes the survival and activation of fibroblasts, thereby driving ECM production.⁴⁰ In scleroderma, fibroblasts express greater amounts of CCL19 than normal fibroblasts.^{82,83} No studies have looked at whether this phenomenon works similarly in chronic RIF.

ADSCs may exert their immunomodulatory effects by downregulating the expression of CCL19, reducing inflammation and subsequent fibrosis. Moreover, the anti-fibrotic properties of ADSCs could indirectly modulate the CCL-19-mediated activation of fibroblasts, further restraining the fibrotic process.⁸⁴

Cell Proliferation and Senescence

There are substantial gaps in understanding how cell senescence modulates regenerative processes. While ageing and dysfunctional tissues are typically associated with the accumulation of senescent cells, particularly as they tend to secrete pro-inflammatory factors,⁸⁵ they may have beneficial roles in promoting homeostasis.⁸⁶

Typically in healthy skin healing, myofibroblasts are driven into senescence at later stages of the process, ceasing to proliferate and upregulating the expression of matrix degrading enzymes (e.g. MMP-2, MMP-3, and MMP-9) while downregulating collagen and TGF- β expression, thereby exerting an anti-fibrotic effect, transforming from ECM-producing cells into ECM-degrading cells, thus imposing a self-limiting control on fibrogenesis. This effect could be missing in chronic RIF. In skin wound healing, this myofibroblast senescence is typically triggered by the dynamically expressed matricellular protein CCN1, and are then sustained by proteins p16 and p21⁸⁶⁻⁸⁸

Key genes controlling these processes include CDKN1A and CDKN2A.

CDKN1A encodes p21, a potent cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor that operates in response to DNA damage, halting the cell cycle progression to allow for repair mechanisms. Radiation exposure induces CDKN1A expression via p53-dependent and -independent pathways, promoting cell cycle arrest and senescence.⁸⁹ Moreover, chronic senescent cell accumulation due to prolonged p21 activation contributes to the secretory phenotype that drives fibrosis.⁹⁰

CDKN2A, on the other hand, encodes p16, which is an essential regulator of the retinoblastoma (Rb) pathway and is often found to be upregulated in RIF. Prolonged p16 expression triggers cellular senescence and augments the release of pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic factors, contributing to fibrogenesis.⁹¹

The interaction between ADSCs and the expression of these genes holds potential therapeutic value, as ADSCs could potentially alleviate fibrosis by reducing the senescent cell burden and dampening the senescence-associated secretory phenotype.⁹² ADSCs have been shown to modulate the cell cycle, likely through paracrine signalling or direct cell contact, which could impact the expression and activation of CDKN1A and CDKN2A⁹³ but up to this point this has not been examined for chronic RIF.

This introduction hopefully illuminates both the complexity of RIF and the substantial therapeutic potential that ADSCs, through their multifaceted interactions and modulatory abilities, may hold in combating this debilitating and disfiguring condition. ADSCs, with their potential to modulate fibrotic processes, stand at the forefront of promising treatments. Yet, the understanding of the complex interplay between ADSCs and chronic RIF pathology is still nascent. This study takes a comprehensive approach to investigate this relationship, first obtaining tissue samples from head and neck cancer patients with RIF, isolating ADSCs and fibroblasts and expanding them in vitro. Through co-culture experiments, similar to those that have so far been conducted for acute RIF, interactions between ADSCs and fibroblasts are assessed. This multi-tiered investigation seeks to further unravel the underlying anti-fibrotic mechanisms and foster a deeper understanding of how ADSCs may potentially improve the treatment of chronic RIF.

Aims & Objectives

Aims

The principal aim of this research was to investigate the cellular mechanisms by which ADSCs modulate the chronic inflammatory response in chronic RIF in head and neck patients. This was accomplished by assessing the interactions between ADSCs and fibroblasts derived from RIF patients in co-culture experiments. The research further aimed to evaluate the impact of ADSCs on the production of procollagen, a key component of the extracellular matrix involved in fibrosis; as well as the clinical outcomes of the original intervention in which cells for the laboratory-based research were collected. Through these investigations, the study sought to contribute to a more detailed understanding of the therapeutic potential of ADSCs in the treatment of RIF.

Objectives

Primary objectives:

- To isolate and expand ADSCs and fibroblasts from tissue samples collected from patients with chronic RIF.
- To examine the direct interactions between ADSCs and fibroblasts in co-culture experiments, with a focus on the modulation of the inflammatory response.
- To assess the impact of ADSCs on the expression of a number of target genes related to inflammation, ECM production, fibroblast transformation, and cellular senescence.
- To evaluate the effects of ADSCs on the production of procollagen using an Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay.

Secondary objectives:

- To compare the gene expression profiles and procollagen production in RIF-derived fibroblasts under different experimental conditions: control, conditioned medium, and co-culture.

- To compare the findings of the in vitro experiments with the clinical outcomes in patients, including objective measurements of skin firmness and elasticity using a Cutometer, as well as subjective patient-reported outcomes.

Null hypotheses

- H0(1): The presence of ADSCs does not significantly alter the gene expression profile or procollagen production in fibroblasts derived from RIF patients.
- H0(2): The observed changes in gene expression and procollagen production do not align with the clinical outcomes in patients.
- H0(3): The in vitro co-culture system does not provide a suitable model for studying the interactions between ADSCs and fibroblasts in RIF.

Materials & Methods

Patient selection

Research ethics committee approval for the project was obtained prior to the project commencing.

Patients are identified monthly for eligibility for autologous fat grafting through joint Plastic and Oral and Maxillofacial surgery joint consultant-led clinics in the Department of Oncology in UCLH's Macmillan Center. Nine of these patients (n=9) were deemed suitable for this study.

These patients had to be at least 3 years post-radiotherapy, without signs of oncological recurrence.

All had severe radiation-induced fibrosis of the head and/or neck that was significantly impacting their quality of life. Only one had had previous lipofilling to the neck.

Laboratory in vitro work

Sample collection

A material transfer agreement was obtained prior to the study commencing.

Fat graft and both healthy and fibrotic skin samples were obtained intraoperatively from blunt abdominal liposuction and incisional biopsies. These matched tissue samples were collected by the author from UCLH theatres and transported to the UCL Royal Free Laboratory. Sterile conditions were maintained as the samples were collected in theatre into Falcon tubes and then aseptic technique was used when unwrapping the samples for processing in the biological safety cabinet.

Isolation of Adipose-Derived Stem Cells (ADSCs)

The isolation of ADSCs was performed through a series of steps (see Figure 5) based upon the original protocol by Zuk et al., and refined by our research team.^{83,94,95} Adipose tissue samples were first washed three times with an equal volume of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and centrifuged

at 300 rpm for 5 minutes to remove debris, discarding the supernatant after each wash. The washed tissue samples were then manually digested by finely chopping them and removing any visible blood vessels if necessary.

Figure 5: ADSC isolation from lipoaspirate (created with BioRender.com).

Next, enzymatic digestion was performed by incubating the samples at 37°C for 30 minutes with 4 mg of collagenase type I. Different sources of collagenase were used in the literature, including 300 U/ml crude collagenase I (Invitrogen), 0.075% collagenase (Life Technologies), and 3000 U/ml type II collagenase digestion buffer (Sigma-Aldrich). Following enzymatic digestion, Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/F-12 (DMEM; ThermoFisher Scientific™) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% glutamine, 1% pen/strep, 1% amphotericin. This was added in a 1:1 volume ratio to deactivate the collagenase.

A red cell lysis step was deemed unnecessary. The digested samples were then filtered through pre-wetted 70 µm cell strainers (BD Biosciences, Oxford, UK) by gently pressing the tissue through the strainer using a syringe plunger. If the strainer became clogged, a new one was used. The filtered samples were centrifuged at 450g for 5 minutes to collect the cells. The supernatant was discarded, and the cell pellet was resuspended.

The resuspended cell pellet was placed in 5 mL of supplemented DMEM/F12 media and cultured in a T25 flask (Corning®). On day 2, the T25 flasks were carefully washed with PBS to remove non-adherent red blood cells. It was recommended to use non-bloody tissue samples to avoid the presence of red blood cells, but naturally, this was not always possible. Those cases that involved greater amounts of blood required more aggressive washing with PBS during the first medium change.

Isolation of Fibroblasts from Skin Samples

Similarly, fibroblasts were isolated from skin samples - unaffected fibroblasts from the umbilical port site normal skin and RIF-affected fibroblasts from the target site of the fat transfer on the head and neck. The skin samples were collected from patients using a sterile biopsy using a scalpel, taking care to minimise contamination and maintain sterility throughout the process. Once collected, the skin samples were washed with sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; ThermoFisher Scientific™) containing antibiotics, such as penicillin and streptomycin, in order to remove any debris and minimise potential contamination.

In a sterile Petri dish, the skin samples were carefully dissected to remove any adipose tissue, blood vessels, and other unwanted components. (Disclaimer: The following steps of fibroblast isolation were not performed by the author but by Dr Marvin Frommer or Professor Xu.) The remaining dermal tissue was then cut into small pieces, approximately 1-2 mm² in size. These small dermal tissue fragments were transferred to a T75 flask that had been coated with a thin layer of collagen or fibronectin to enhance cell attachment and promote the outgrowth of fibroblasts from the tissue fragments.

The flask was filled with Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and antibiotics, such as penicillin and streptomycin, to provide an optimal environment for fibroblast growth. The flask was then incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. The tissue fragments were monitored daily for fibroblast outgrowth, which typically appeared as spindle-shaped cells emerging from the edges of the tissue fragments and migrating onto the flask surface.

When the fibroblasts reached approximately 80% confluence, they were subcultured by removing the culture medium, washing with PBS, and applying trypsin-EDTA solution to detach the cells from the flask surface. The detached cells were then transferred to a new, larger tissue culture flask (T150) with fresh DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and antibiotics for further expansion. Fibroblasts at passages 2-3 were typically used for experimental purposes to ensure a consistent cell population with minimal influence from the initial tissue explant.

Cell culture and expansion

Cell culture medium was changed every 48-72 hours.

At > 80% confluence, the cells were passaged — harvested, split into two portions and reseeded into two daughter cell culture flasks. To detach cells from the flask glass, medium was removed, they were washed with PBS to remove residual cell media and afterwards incubated with 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA (Sigma-Aldrich) for 5 minutes at 37°C (The volume of trypsin needed corresponded to the size of the flask: T25 → 2mL, T75 → 4mL, T150 → 6mL). Following the incubation period, an equal volume of culture medium was added to the flask to deactivate the trypsin. Cells were spun at 300rpm for 5 minutes, medium was removed, and the cell pellet was resuspended in 1 mL of culture medium. This was then split between the two new culture flasks.

Once a T150 flask (Vent Cap, Corning) reached 80% confluency, it was deemed ready to be frozen or used in the experiment.

Freezing between sample collection

Following the isolation and culture of ADSCs, the cells were prepared for cryopreservation using the following procedure:

The cell culture medium was first removed from the T25 flask, followed by a 2 mL PBS wash to ensure proper trypsin function. Next, 2 mL of trypsin was added to the T25 flask (4 mL for T75 flasks) and incubated for 5 minutes. The flasks were then checked to ensure the cells had lifted and were no longer adherent. If necessary, the sides of the flasks were gently tapped to facilitate detachment.

To deactivate the trypsin, an equal volume of cell culture (to the original volume of trypsin used) was added to the flasks, and the cell suspension was transferred to a 15 mL centrifuge tube. The volume in the tube was then adjusted to a total of 10 mL with cell culture medium. Additional medium could be added directly to the flask to help remove any remaining cells, but the final volume in the centrifuge tube could not exceed 10 mL. After lifting the cells, the original flask was checked to ensure no cells were left behind.

After centrifugation, the supernatant was carefully removed without disturbing the cell pellet, as the regular culture medium is not suitable for freezing. The cell pellet was then resuspended in 1 mL of Cryo-SFM freezing medium.

2mL cryovials (Alpha Laboratories LW3335) were used for storing the cell suspension. For T150 flasks, the resuspended cells were divided equally between two cryovials (0.5 mL in each). Once the cells were resuspended in the freezing medium, they were quickly transferred to a Mr Frosty container and placed in a -80°C freezer. This was done rapidly, to preserve cell viability. Subsequently, the cryovials were transferred to a liquid nitrogen tank for long-term storage.

Characterisation

For the characterisation of the cells utilised in the in vitro study, flow cytometry was performed (Disclosure: This was performed by Dr Marvin Frommer). Each sample consisted of 105 ADSCs at passage 2-4. Following their retrieval from liquid nitrogen storage, the cells were deposited into Eppendorf tubes.

Approximately 24 hours prior to flow cytometric analysis, cells were stained with anti-human antibodies for various CD antigens, supplied by Myltenyi Biotec. These included CD90 FITC REAfinity™, CD73 PE REAfinity™, CD105 APC REAfinity™, CD34 PE-Vio® 615 REAfinity™, CD31 VioBlue® REAfinity™, and CD45 VioGreen™ REAfinity™. Additionally, the 7-AAD Viability Staining Solution from BioLegend® was used to identify live cells.

Flow cytometry was performed using the BD LSRFortessa™ X-20 Cell Analyzer from BD Biosystems. Each sample was divided for different purposes: 50,000 cells were allocated for analysis and the remainder for bead compensation.

The staining procedure was as follows:

1. A single cell suspension was created and washed three times with cell staining buffer at 350 x g for 5 minutes.
2. Aliquots of 10⁵ cells in 100 μ L were prepared in Eppendorf tubes.
3. Fc receptors were blocked by incubating with 100ng of IgG for 5-15 minutes at room temperature. This step was followed without any washing.
4. 2 μ L of each of the conjugated antibodies and 84 μ L of cell staining buffer were added, followed by vortexing. The suspension was incubated on ice in the dark for 20 minutes.
5. Unbound antibodies were removed by washing three times in 2 mL of FC staining buffer at 350 g for 5 minutes.
6. Cells were resuspended in 500 μ L of FC fixation buffer and left overnight.
7. The next day, cells were vortexed and transferred to FACS tubes.
8. Flow cytometry was performed.

Data analysis was executed using FlowJo™ v.10.8.1 from BD Biosystems. The samples were processed to eliminate cell debris, cell duplets, and dead cells. Live cells were identified as those with a fluorescence value of < 10³ for 7-AAD. Sequential gating was then used to identify cells positive for CD73⁺ and CD90⁺ and negative for CD45⁻ and CD31⁻, with a threshold fluorescence of 10³. Further analysis was then conducted on these populations.

Experimental setup

The experiments were prepared as shown in Figure 6. Cells used for the experiments were at low passage (P) 2-4, as the greater the passage, the higher the likelihood of the phenotype and cell behaviour changing in vitro from the conditions being modelled.⁹⁶

Figure 6: 6-well plate experimental setup. Fibroblasts and ADSCs are seeded independently at a seeding density of 100 000 cells per well and then on day 4, the RIF fibroblasts were treated with conditioned media or ADSCs on transwells. (Created using BioRender.com)

On Day 1, ADSCs for conditioned media (CM) production were seeded in a 6-well plate in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) at a density of 100,000 cells per well.

On Day 2, the media for the ADSCs was changed to DMEM with 0.1% FBS. Concurrently, three plates of fibroblasts were seeded at a density of 100,000 cells per well, and ADSCs were seeded onto transwell inserts at the same density on a fifth plate.

On Day 3, the media for both the fibroblasts and the ADSCs on transwell inserts was changed to DMEM with 0.1% FBS.

Day 4 marked the treatment day, during which ADSC-conditioned media (ADSC-CM) was collected, and the treatment of fibroblasts was initiated. The control group received a media change, while the co-culture group had the media changed and ADSC transwell inserts placed inside. The CM for the co-culture group was centrifuged at 3,000g for 10 minutes before use.

Day 5 involved waiting, while on Day 6, samples were harvested. This process included isolating RNA and collecting supernatants, which were then stored at -80°C for future analyses.

In total, the experiment required 1,800,000 fibroblasts, divided into three groups with six wells each (100,000 cells per well), and 1,200,000 ADSCs, divided into two groups with six wells each (100,000 cells per well). Since in practice this meant that two T150s of ADSCs and two T150s of fibroblasts at 80% confluence were required per patient. This was very much the limiting factor for initiating the co-culture experiment. Given the diseased nature of the RIF fibroblasts, this was difficult to achieve for the majority of the patients in a timely manner.

Consequently, only tissue from patients 1,3, and 6 could be co-cultured and this had to be staggered over several weeks. The fate of the other fibroblasts is summarised in table 1.

Patient	Date of operation	Location of lipotransfer	ADSCs	Fibroblasts	Tissue included?
1	24.1	Neck	expanded & frozen	expanded & frozen	✓
2	24.1	Face & Neck	expanded & frozen	Could not be grown	
3	28.2	Tongue & Neck	expanded & frozen	expanded & frozen	✓
4	28.3	Neck	expanded & frozen	Lost to infection	
5	28.3	Neck	expanded & frozen	growing slowly	
6	25.4	Neck	expanded & frozen	growing well	✓
7	23.5	Face & Neck	expanded & frozen	growing slowly	
8	23.5	Neck	expanded & frozen	growing slowly	
9	31.5	Face & Neck	expanded & frozen	growing slowly	

Table 1: Patient tissue isolation and expansion progress.

RNA extraction

The analysis of gene expression was performed through the utilization of qRT-PCR. After storing the supernatants for subsequent ELISA analysis, all plates were cooled on ice and twice cleansed with PBS.

Total RNA was extracted using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen), in compliance with the manufacturer's recommended protocols. Five of the wells were treated with 350µL of RLT buffer with BME additive, where each row represented a unique experimental group on the well plate. Two of these wells were destined for future bulk sequencing analysis (arrangements for this are still being made, as the analysis will only be possible after the accumulation of all project samples from our wider research group). The last well had 120µL of radioimmunoprecipitation assay Lysis and Extraction Buffer (RIPA, Sigma Aldrich) added to it instead for total protein analysis.

The wells were then scrupulously scraped and harvested into Eppendorf tubes, and a light microscope was used to verify that no cells remained. The samples were conserved at -80°C for subsequent analyses (see figure 7).

Figure 7: Summary of well destiny for downstream analysis (Created using BioRender.com)

Prior to engaging in downstream assessments, the samples were allowed to defrost on ice, followed by these procedures:

1. A volume of 350 μ L of RNA sample was transferred to RNeasy mini spin columns in collection tubes.
2. 350 μ L of 70% ethanol was added to the RNA sample, then centrifuged for 15 seconds at 4°C and 8,000 x g. The fluid from the collection column was removed.
3. 700 μ L of RW1 buffer was added and centrifuged as above, and the fluid in the collection column was removed.
4. 500 μ L of RPE buffer was introduced and centrifuged as above, and the fluid in the collection column was removed.
5. This process was repeated with another 500 μ L of RPE buffer, but the centrifugation time was increased to 2 minutes. The fluid in the collection column was removed.
6. Then, the lower collection column was replaced, and the sample was centrifuged without any additives for 1 minute to dry the membrane.
7. Finally, the lower collection column was swapped for a 1.5 mL sealable collection tube. 30 μ L of RNase-free water was added, and the sample was centrifuged for 1 minute.
8. The spin column was disposed of, and the Eppendorf tubes were closed.

Following the extraction of total RNA, the concentration and the quality of the acquired RNA were measured with a NanoDrop spectrophotometer.

To carry out the analysis of gene expression, the QuantiFast SYBR Green PCR Kit (Qiagen) and gene-specific QuantiTect Primer Assays (Qiagen) were used. The primer assays were designed to target these genes: COL1A1, TGF β 1, ACTA2, MMP-1, MMP-9, TNC, CCL-19, CDKN2A, CDKN1A, and the housekeeping gene B2M (see table 4 of the appendix). The qRT-PCR was executed using a real-time PCR system, with each sample being analysed in duplicate for each target gene. The cycling conditions were established per the instructions provided by the QuantiFast SYBR Green PCR Kit. The gene expression levels were normalised using the housekeeping gene B2M, and the relative expression levels were calculated using the $2^{(-\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ method.

Extraction and quantification of protein

As mentioned above, total protein was procured from the cells developed in a monolayer by adding 120 μ L of RIPA to one of the wells of each plate. The wells were then comprehensively scraped, transferred to an Eppendorf tube and frozen.

Figure 8: Concentrations of the Pierce™ BSA protein standards (displayed on the x-axis) were correlated with their corresponding absorbance values recorded at 562nm (displayed on the y-axis). By applying a regression line to the gathered data points, a regression equation was established. This equation was subsequently utilized to ascertain the protein concentrations within the cell lysates.

At a later stage, protein concentrations from the obtained cell lysates were determined using the Pierce™ BCA Protein Assay (ThermoFisher Scientific™). The BCA working reagent was prepared by mixing 50 parts of BCA Reagent A with 1 part of Reagent B (50:1, A:B ratio). A standard curve was established using pre-diluted Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) standards (0-2000 μ g/mL; ThermoFisher Scientific™). The standards and the cell lysates were added to a 96-well plate in duplicates along with the BCA working reagent, forming the basis for colorimetric analysis. The plate was then incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes to promote the formation of a copper ion-protein complex which reacts with BCA to produce a color change. Absorbance was measured at 560 nm using a Mithras LB 940 Multimode Microplate Reader (Berthold Technologies). The mean absorbance values from the duplicates were calculated and plotted against the BSA standard values to generate a standard curve (see figure 8). The protein concentration of the lysates was determined

by interpolation from the standard curve. The quantified total protein values were subsequently used to normalize the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) data to account for differences in protein content between samples.

Quantitative Real-Time Polymerase Chain Reaction (qRT-PCR)

The RT-qPCR process was executed on the refined RNA samples to analyse the mRNA expression of pertinent genes using the QuantiNova SYBR Green® RT-PCR Kit (Qiagen). This kit simplifies the procedure by allowing the reverse transcription of mRNA to cDNA and PCR amplification within the same tube. All primers were sourced from Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT™) as independent forward and reverse products, except for the CDKN2A and CDKN1A, which were supplied as a single mix. Primers were prepared with RNase-free water (Qiagen) following the manufacturer's guidelines.

For target genes *COL1A1*, *TGFβ1*, *ACTA2*, *MMP-1*, *MMP-9*, *TNC*, and *CCL-19*, the following was included per tube to achieve a total volume of 12µl:

- To create the 10µl of reactant solution:
 - 3.14µL of RNase-free water
 - 6µL of QuantiNova SYBR Green® PCR Master Mix
 - 0.12µL of QuantiNova RT Mix
 - 0.12µL of forward primer
 - 0.12µL of reverse primer
 - 0.5µL of ROX dye
- 2µL of 1:10 diluted RNA (RNA: RNase-free water ratio)

In order to make up the CDKN2A and CDKN1A, the proportions were slightly different:

- To create the 10µl of reactant solution:
 - 2.18µL of RNase-free water

- 6 μ L of QuantiNova SYBR Green® PCR Master Mix
- 0.12 μ L of QuantiNova RT Mix
- 1.2 μ L of combined primer
- 0.5 μ L of ROX dye
- 2 μ L of 1:10 diluted RNA (RNA: RNase-free water ratio)

The RT-qPCR process was executed in duplicate for each gene of interest using the StepOne (Applied biosystems). The protocol entailed reverse transcription at 50°C for 10 minutes, initial activation at 95°C for 5 minutes, followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 10 seconds and combined annealing/extension at 60°C for 30 seconds. The generation of Threshold cycle (Ct) values for the genes of interest and the B2M was followed by determining the mRNA expression level of the genes of interest relative to the expression of the housekeeping gene B2M using the delta Ct method ($2^{-\Delta Ct}$ method).

Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)

The levels of secreted proteins in the co-culture supernatants was measured using a commercial ELISA procollagen a1 kit (Human Pro-Collagen I alpha 1 DuoSet ELISA, R&D systems), following the manufacturers' protocols. Each sample was analysed in triplicate for each target protein.

Briefly, 96-well microplates were coated with the capture antibody and then left to incubate overnight at 4°C or for a few hours at room temperature. Wells were washed with a wash buffer and blocked with a blocking buffer to minimise non-specific binding. Samples and standards were added to the appropriate wells in triplicate and incubated for 2 hours at room temperature. Following sample incubation, the wells were washed, and a detection antibody was added to each well. After a 2-hour incubation at room temperature, the wells were rewashed, and the substrate solution was added. The enzymatic reaction was stopped after 20-30 minutes using the stop solution. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a plate reader, and the protein concentrations were determined using the standard curve generated from the standards.

Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted using 3 biological replicates (n=3) for each of the three experimental conditions, with duplicate technical replicates for qRT-PCR and triplicate technical replicates for ELISA. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tests, and results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Differences were considered statistically significant as described in table 2.

Levels of significance	Denoted by
p>0.05 (Not significant)	ns
p<0.05	*
p<0.01	**
p<0.001	***

Table 2: Levels of significance

Data analysis was conducted using GraphPad Prism.

For qRT-PCR data, relative gene expression levels were calculated using the $2^{(-\Delta\Delta Ct)}$ method, with beta2-microglobulin as the reference gene. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine any significant differences in gene expression levels among the experimental conditions.

For ELISA data, protein concentrations were determined from absorbance values using the standard curve generated from the standards. Once again, one-way ANOVA was performed to assess significant differences in protein levels among the experimental conditions.

Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or standard error of the mean (SEM), as appropriate. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. Graphs were generated to display the results, including bar charts or box plots to show the distribution of the data and any significant differences between the experimental groups.

In cases where data was not normally distributed or variance homogeneity was not met, non-parametric tests such as the Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's post hoc test for multiple comparisons were employed.

Correlation between in vitro findings and clinical outcomes

Given that potentially up to a third of the patients treated with AFT may not respond to initial treatment,¹¹ it was deemed wise to attempt to correlate the interim clinical outcomes with the laboratory findings. If they were found to be non-responders, then the results would potentially have to be examined in two groups.

Many factors such as advanced age, chemotherapy, older radiotherapy techniques, previous surgery, larger tumour volumes, as well as individual radio-sensitivity and other genetic predisposing factors all impact the severity of RIF of the head and neck.⁴ A certain portion of the severity of these symptoms is quantifiable but others like pain are much more subjective. Therefore, measuring improvement requires a mixture of objective and subjective methods of evaluating improvement in the patient's clinical condition. Therefore both interim subjective patient observations and objective skin property measurements (see figure 9) were utilised. It must be noted that due to the fact that this is a part of a greater ongoing study and given that this chronic process is often slow to respond to treatment (other studies and the team's previous experience have found that significant improvement is not usually notable until at least 6 months after fat transfer⁹⁷), this data was collected cautiously with the knowledge that the results would be preliminary in mind. It should also be noted that all data collected was collected jointly together with Dr Ahmad Abul and Professor Peter Butler at the UCLH Macmillan Cancer Center, in joint OMFS and Plastic surgery Clinics.

Figure 9: The Cutometer® creates negative pressure, drawing the skin into the probe's aperture. The skin's resistance to this suction indicates its firmness, while its ability to return to its original state reflects its elasticity. An internal optical system measures the distance the skin travels into the aperture, with the results displayed as a curve. This data is used to calculate a series of parameters, including R-parameters, F-parameters, and Q-parameters.

The R-parameters are calculated using various measurements taken during the suction and relaxation periods. U_f is the total distance the skin stretches after the suction period, while U_a is the total distance the skin retracts back to its normal position at the end of the relaxation period. U_e represents the initial skin stretch during the first 0.1 seconds of suction, while U_v is the distance the skin stretches between the first 0.1 seconds and the end of the suction phase. U_r is the distance the skin retracts in the first 0.1 seconds of the relaxation phase. These measurements provide insights into the skin's elasticity, firmness, and other mechanical properties.⁹⁸ (Original figure drawn in Vectornator).

The Cutometer® measures various parameters that reflect the biomechanical properties of the skin, with each parameter (R0 to R9) providing insights into aspects of skin elasticity and firmness. It works by applying a negative pressure to the skin, causing it to deform into the aperture of the probe. The extent and speed of this deformation, as well as the skin's ability to return to its original state, are measured and used to calculate various parameters related to the skin's mechanical properties. While the Cutometer® can also provide F- and Q- values that represent more complex viscoelastic properties of the skin, this analysis focused on the more direct and clinically interpretable R-values.

The sternocleidomastoid (SCM) area was chosen as a consistent site for Cutometer measurements due to its relevance in this patient population. All patients in this study had chronic RIF of the neck that involved the SCM area, and each patient received fat grafting to this location. In contrast, not all patients had facial or trapezius involvement for example. Thus, focusing on the SCM area allowed for consistent and comparable measurements across all patients, while also ensuring the area of interest was one directly impacted by the fibrotic condition and the treatment intervention.

Results

Gene expression Analysis

The potential modulatory effect of ADSCs on chronic RIF was examined through the gene expression of *COL1A1*, *TGFβ1*, *ACTA2*, *MMP-1*, *MMP-9*, *TNC*, *CCL-19*, *CDKN2A*, and *CDKN1A* across three experimental conditions—RIF control, conditioned medium, and co-culture. Each condition was tested in both normal human dermal fibroblasts (HDFs) and RIF-derived fibroblasts. For comparative analysis, gene expression under each condition was compared to normal fibroblasts under control conditions, serving as the baseline.

The RTqPCR revealed the following (see figure 10 for an overview of PCR findings; refer to Appendix figure 1 for more details):

Figure 10: Chronic RIF overview of PCR results (n=3; duplicate technical repeats): A series of nine bar graphs, each representing the relative expression of a specific target gene: *COL1A1*, *TGFB1*, *ACTA2*, *MMP1*, *MMP9*, *TNC*, *CCL19*, *CDKN1A*, and *CDKN2A*. Each graph is divided into three experimental conditions: RIF control, conditioned medium, and co-culture, each tested in both normal and RIF-derived human dermal fibroblasts (HDFs). The height of each bar signifies the mean expression level, while the error bars indicate the standard deviation, providing a visualization of the gene expression variance. Notable patterns include a significant reduction in *COL1A1* expression in RIF fibroblasts under CM and CC conditions, a significant differential expression of *ACTA2* between normal and RIF control conditions, and a significant variance in *MMP1* expression across conditions. The remaining genes do not show significant variations in their expression profiles across the three experimental conditions.

The most significant finding emerged from the *COL1A1* expression analysis. There was a significant difference in *COL1A1* gene expression, which is important in ECM production, across the experimental conditions (Kruskal-Wallis test, $P < 0.05$). More specifically, in comparison to the RIF control, there was a significantly lower *COL1A1* expression in both the conditioned media (Adjusted P Value = 0.0090) and co-culture conditions (Adjusted P Value = 0.0033). However, no significant difference was detected between the RIF control and normal HDFs (Adjusted P Value = 0.0916). This would suggest that the presence of ADSCs in the conditioned medium and co-culture conditions resulted in a significant reduction in *COL1A1* expression in fibroblasts from RIF patients (Adjusted P Values of 0.0090 and 0.0033 respectively), aligning the expression closer to levels found in normal fibroblasts.

This molecular response to ADSCs was further scrutinised through the lens of genes associated with fibroblast transformation, specifically *TGFBI* and *ACTA2*. Expression of *TGFBI* did not show significant variation across the conditions (Kruskal-Wallis test, $P > 0.05$). However, a descriptive examination of the data does reveal a reduction in *TGFBI* expression in both the conditioned media and co-culture conditions compared to the RIF control. This observation suggests a possible trend towards normalisation of the *TGFBI* expression that could be confirmed with larger sample sizes. Similarly, *ACTA2* expression presented an interesting pattern, with the Kruskal-Wallis test revealing a statistically significant difference across the experimental conditions in *ACTA2* gene expression ($P = 0.024$). This suggests that at least one experimental condition influenced the *ACTA2* expression in a distinct way. Yet, a more specific pairwise comparison using Dunn's test did not identify significant differences in *ACTA2* expression when comparing the RIF control to the other conditions (Normal, Conditioned Medium, and Co-Culture, Adjusted P Values = 0.5535, 0.7865, and 0.2937 respectively). This indicates that while a significant effect was observed overall, the modulation of *ACTA2* expression by ADSCs is complex and cannot be clearly elucidated by comparing only two conditions at a time.

In terms of ECM remodelling, the genes *MMP1* and *MMP9* were investigated. *MMP1* expression varied significantly between normal and diseased fibroblasts but not between experimental conditions; it was significantly less expressed in RIF-affected groups than in normal fibroblasts. *MMP9* showed a statistically significant response to conditioned media; however, notably, the relative quantity of *MMP9* expression compared to the housekeeping gene was very low across the board.

Expression of *TNC* appeared to be upregulated in the ADSC treated conditions (in conditioned media and in the co-culture) compared to the normal and control RIF fibroblasts. Despite the variation across conditions, *TNC* expression did not demonstrate significant changes (Kruskal-Wallis test, $P = 0.1201$).

In the examination of *CCL19*, a chemokine important in the recruitment and activation of immune cells during tissue repair and fibrosis, the results indicated a different pattern. The Kruskal-Wallis test did not identify a significant difference in *CCL19* expression across the experimental conditions ($P = 0.2246$). This lack of significance was further supported by the Dunn's multiple comparisons test, which showed no significant pairwise differences when comparing the RIF control to the Normal, Conditioned Medium, and Co-culture conditions (Adjusted *P* Values > 0.9999 , > 0.9999 , and 0.6870 respectively), thus suggesting that, under the conditions tested, ADSCs do not have a significant modulatory effect on *CCL19* expression in fibroblasts from RIF patients.

Lastly, the impact of the different conditions on the expression of cell cycle inhibitors, *CDKN1A* and *CDKN2A* was also investigated. Surprisingly, neither of these key regulators of cell cycle and senescence showed significant changes in expression across the conditions. For *CDKN1A*, the Kruskal-Wallis test produced a *P* value of 0.9024 , indicating a lack of significant difference between the groups. Dunn's multiple comparisons test further supported this, as no significant differences were observed when the RIF control group was compared with the Normal, Conditioned Medium, and Co-Culture conditions (Adjusted *P* Values > 0.9999 for all comparisons).

In the analysis of *CDKN2A* expression, a similar trend was observed. The Kruskal-Wallis test resulted in a *P* value of 0.9951 , suggesting no significant differences in *CDKN2A* expression between the groups. This was consistent with the results from Dunn's multiple comparisons test, where no significant pairwise differences were identified (Adjusted *P* Values > 0.9999 for all comparisons).

Secreted Protein Analysis

Figure 11: ELISA results (n=3; triplicate technical repeats): Pro-collagen levels measured by ELISA in normal HDFs, RIF Control HDFs, RIF HDFs treated with ADSC Conditioned Medium, and RIF HDFs grown in Co-culture with ADSCs on transwells. Each condition is illustrated by a distinct bar, with error bars signifying the standard error of the mean (SEM) for each condition. Notably, pro-collagen levels varied significantly among the different conditions (Kruskal-Wallis test, $P < 0.0001$). Post-hoc Dunn's multiple comparison tests showed significant differences in pro-collagen levels between the RIF control condition and both the Conditioned Medium ($P=0.0008$) and Co-culture conditions ($P=0.0005$). These results highlight the elevated pro-collagen levels in the Co-culture condition compared to the others, with the least amount in the Normal condition.

The secretion of proteins related to the previously studied genes by the in vitro ADSCs was probed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs). While ELISAs were planned for each of the nine genes studied, funding and time constraints of the MSc meant that only the procollagen ELISA was conducted (see figure 11). The protein levels discovered in the ADSCs supernatant were subsequently adjusted in relation to the total protein amount found in the wells, in order to standardise protein secretion according to cell count.

In an effort to substantiate the PCR findings, the concentration of procollagen, a precursor to type I collagen and encoded by the *COL1A1* gene, was examined. The choice to assess procollagen was dictated by two main factors. First, the *COL1A1* gene demonstrated the most significant difference in expression across the experimental conditions in the PCR analysis. Second, the measurement of procollagen, as a direct product of COL1A1 expression, could provide a more tangible, protein-level understanding of the dynamics observed at the gene expression level.

The procollagen ELISA results, which have been normalized to total protein, indicate a significant variation in procollagen levels across the different experimental conditions, as confirmed by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($P < 0.0001$). Dunn's multiple comparisons test, which adjusts for multiple testing, revealed significant differences in procollagen concentrations between the RIF control and both the Conditioned Medium (Adjusted P Value = 0.0008) and Co-culture conditions (Adjusted P Value = 0.0005). However, no significant difference was observed when comparing the RIF control to the Normal condition (Adjusted P Value > 0.9999). These findings suggest that the ADSCs in the conditioned medium and co-culture conditions significantly enhance the production of procollagen in fibroblasts derived from RIF patients.

Flow Cytometry Analysis

In order to characterise the ADSCs used in this study, flow cytometry was performed to identify the expression of specific CD markers. The 99.7% of live single cells were negative for haematopoietic markers CD45 and CD31 and positive for stromal markers CD90 and CD73, consistent with the expected phenotype of ADSCs. Of these, 65.7% were positive for both CD34 and CD105, suggesting the presence of a potential early progenitor or stem cell population. A more detailed breakdown of the flow cytometry results can be found in the appendix (see appendix figure 2 and accompanying text).

Clinical outcomes

Having demonstrated the effects of ADSCs on fibroblast behaviour at the molecular level in vitro, the study then sought to evaluate the clinical outcomes of patients had undergone AFG. Patients either had fat grafting only in the neck (n=5), in both the face and neck (n=3), or to the tongue as well as the neck (n=1).

Three months post-treatment, subjective feedback was gathered from 5 of these patients regarding their impressions of improvement. The majority of patients reported perceiving a positive change in their condition. Specifically, patients often voluntarily quantified their observed improvements to be in the range of a 5-15% enhancement, mostly in terms of improved range of movement or skin texture. One patient reported less frequent muscle spasms, which had been one of their primary concerns. It is important to note that one patient was lost to follow-up and it was too early to evaluate three others at the time of data collection.

Patient	Date of operation	Location of lipotransfer	Subjective impression at 3 month check-up
1	24.1	Neck	subjective improvement
2	24.1	Face & Neck	patient lost to follow-up
3	28.2	Tongue & Neck	subjective improvement (teleconsultation)
4	28.3	Neck	subjective improvement
5	28.3	Neck	subjective improvement
6	25.4	Neck	subjective improvement
7	23.5	Face & Neck	Too early to evaluate
8	23.5	Neck	Too early to evaluate
9	31.5	Face & Neck	Too early to evaluate

Despite this promising anecdotal evidence, it was important to couple this subjective analysis with objective measures. The Cutometer was used to evaluate the biomechanical properties of skin in the sternocleidomastoid (SCM) region of 3 patients, before and after autologous fat grafting at the 3-months postoperative follow-up (see figure 12).

In the preliminary pre and post-operative Cutometer readings, the sternocleidomastoid region demonstrated no statistically significant difference across the parameters. However, a closer examination of the data reveals nuanced changes in skin properties. The Autologous Fat Grafting (AFG) appears to have resulted in an overall improvement in skin viscoelasticity and resilience to repeated deformation, as evidenced by increases in R2, R5, R6, R7, and R8 parameters. These changes suggest that the skin has become more capable of withstanding strain and recovering its shape.

Conversely, decreases in R0, R1, R3, and R4 parameters indicate that the skin has become less firm and shows less fatigue after repeated strain. It also appears less able to return to its original state

after deformation. While these changes might initially seem negative, they align with the procedure's goal of reducing skin rigidity, thus can be interpreted as positive outcomes.

The mean difference between pre and post-operative measurements was -0.1502, with a standard deviation of 0.4204. The 95% confidence interval ranged from -0.4509 to 0.1505, and the R squared value (partial eta squared) was 0.1242. The correlation coefficient (r) was 0.06584, with a one-tailed P value of 0.4283, indicating that the pairing was not significantly effective. Despite this, the observed changes in individual parameters suggest that the AFG had beneficial effects on skin properties overall.

Figure 12: Plot of pre-operative and post-operative Cutometer measurements in (n=3) patients with RIF of the head and neck. Each parameter (R0 to R9) is plotted on the x-axis, while the y-axis represents the measurement value. Paired observations from the same patient are connected by lines, with pre-operative measurements represented by empty circular markers and post-operative measurements by filled-in circle markers. This plot provides a visual representation of the observed trends in changes across various Cutometer parameters following autologous fat grafting. Note the overall trend towards increased post-operative values in several parameters, despite the lack of statistical significance, suggesting potential enhancements in skin's biomechanical properties. The variability and spread of the measurements are also visually depicted, highlighting the preliminary nature of these results and the need for further investigations with larger patient cohorts.

Discussion

The principal results of this study demonstrate a significant modulatory influence of ADSCs on the gene expression profile and ECM remodelling of fibroblasts derived from chronic RIF tissues, a finding that aligns with the emerging paradigm of ADSCs as critical players in tissue regeneration and repair.⁹⁹

Changes in Collagen

A key observation from the study was the significant reduction in *COL1A1* gene expression, encoding the pro-alpha1 chains of type I collagen, in RIF fibroblasts exposed to ADSCs, either in co-culture or conditioned media conditions. This aligns with the existing literature that suggests that ADSCs can modulate the expression of profibrotic genes and promote ECM remodelling through secreted exosomes, both in the skin¹⁰⁰ and in other organs.⁷³ By attenuating the *COL1A1* gene expression, ADSCs could potentially hinder excessive collagen accumulation, a hallmark of fibrotic disorders, which can help restore the ECM architecture and promote functional recovery of RIF-affected tissues.⁴⁸

Surprisingly, despite the reduction in *COL1A1* gene expression, the procollagen production was significantly enhanced in ADSC-treated conditions. This initially seems at odds with the gene expression results. However, it could suggest that the the ADSCs may be influencing procollagen production through post-transcriptional mechanisms or contributing to procollagen production themselves, a hypothesis that is supported by studies highlighting the paracrine and autocrine roles of ADSCs in ECM production and remodelling. In particular, recent differential gene expression analysis of ADSCs has shown that they express *COL1A1*.⁸³

Similar findings have actually been reported previously by Brongo et al's histology findings in severe burns treated with lipofilling, with new collagen deposition being noted.¹⁰¹ Other studies looking at fat grafting in scarred tissues showed that it leads to histological changes including a reappearance of the papillary dermis,¹⁰² reduction in dermoepidermal junction flattening, restoration of a normal ridge pattern, and elongation of the epidermal crest,¹⁰³ despite a decrease in dermal thickness.¹⁰⁴ The conclusion from all of these findings is potentially that the procedure reduces dermal collagen content overall, yet improves its organisation and sometimes results in new collagen deposition in the context of tissue regeneration.

Possible interactions with the TGF- β /Smad axis

Primarily involved in wound healing, the TGF- β /Smad axis can lead to pathological healing patterns when dysregulated, such as those observed in excessive scarring conditions. The administration of ADSCs has previously been linked with a decrease in *TGFBI* expression, an essential element of this fibrotic process.^{105,106}

Interestingly, while there was no statistically significant reduction in the expression of *TGFBI*,¹⁰⁷ a descriptive examination of the data suggests a trend towards normalisation of *TGFBI* expression in the ADSC-treated conditions. Although this observation would need validation in larger cohorts, it is consistent with studies suggesting that ADSCs can modulate TGF- β 1 signalling and mitigate its fibrogenic effects.¹⁰⁸

However, this is a reductionist statement, as Borovikova et al noted in their 2017 review, “the interactions of ADSCs with members of the TGF- β family seem to be far more complex than a simple 1-way inhibition.”²¹

As for *ACTA2*, the findings suggest a complex modulation by ADSCs that cannot be clearly elucidated with pairwise comparisons. Such complexity is not unexpected as studies have reported the multifaceted nature of ADSC-mediated effects on myofibroblast differentiation,¹⁰⁹ suggesting that several factors, including the state of fibroblasts, ADSC characteristics, and the microenvironment, could collectively influence the modulation of *ACTA2* expression. However, just like with the *TGFBI*, there is a general descriptive downward trend, which is in keeping with the existing literature, such as reports by Finsson et al. that α -SMA seems to be decreased after fat grafting.¹¹⁰

Matrix remodelling

As was previously stated, MMPs and their TIMPs play an intricate role in ECM remodelling during tissue repair and fibrosis in a complex cascade that in extreme reductionist terms can be described as: MMPs degrade various ECM components, including collagen, facilitating tissue remodelling, while TIMPs control MMP activity to prevent excessive degradation of ECM.⁷¹

Under normal conditions, *MMP1* is crucial for the remodelling of the ECM, particularly in the degradation of interstitial collagens such as type I, II, and III collagens. This role allows for regular tissue repair and renewal.^{111,112} In the case of chronic RIF, an ongoing inflammatory response and aberrant tissue remodelling take place, leading to altered MMP activity relative to normal tissue.¹¹³ The fact that the results imply that the *MMP1* is higher in the normal fibroblasts than in the chronic RIF fibroblasts is interesting, as many chronic wounds, particularly non-healing wounds exhibit upregulated *MMP1*.¹¹⁴ However, naturally not all chronic wounds are alike and fibrotic conditions have a particular pathogenesis. While there was no other specific mention of this available in the literature related to RIF, a study of fibrotic conditions of the liver previously noted that the expression of the MMP-1 gene is known to be remarkably increased in fibroblasts in hepatic fibrosis, but not in those with liver cirrhosis.¹¹⁵ Theoretically, this downregulation of *MMP1* could be a consequence of prolonged TGF- β signalling. TGF- β is known to suppress *MMP1* expression while promoting the expression of TIMPs, tipping the balance toward ECM accumulation and fibrosis.¹¹⁶

MMP9 expression on the other hand exhibited significant downregulation in the ADSC-conditioned medium group. This is somewhat puzzling given that the change in *TGFB1* expression was not significant in the results and that the proposed cause of excess matrix deposition in RIF is TGF- β reducing the activity of *MMP2* and *MMP9*.¹¹⁷ As we established in the introduction, *MMP9* is a known regulator of ECM homeostasis, playing a complex and dual role in fibrosis. It is generally upregulated during the initial stages of tissue injury, contributing to the development of fibrosis by facilitating ECM degradation, inflammatory cell migration, and the subsequent activation of pro-fibrotic factors such as TGF- β .¹¹⁸ However, on the other hand, *MMP9* can also play a role in the resolution of fibrosis by breaking down the excessive ECM produced during the fibrotic process. In this regard, *MMP9* helps to restore normal tissue architecture. However, this role is generally overshadowed by its pro-fibrotic effects in the early stages of injury.¹¹⁹ Our observations seem to align with the former role and to suggest that secreted factors from ADSCs may have a regulatory effect on *MMP9*, potentially leading to the attenuation of fibrosis.

Initial clues pointing to more complex mechanisms

The upregulation of *TNC* in the ADSC-treated conditions, although statistically non-significant, aligns with studies suggesting that TNC, an ECM glycoprotein, can be modulated by stem cells and may contribute to tissue repair and regeneration.⁶⁹ This correlates with findings by Fuku et al., that showed *TNC* upregulation in ADSC spheroids when treating other inflammatory conditions.⁶⁶ However, it is at odds with studies that have found TCN to be a major driver of fibrosis, and that mice lacking TNC showed attenuation of skin and lung fibrosis, and accelerated fibrosis resolution.⁶⁸ A study by Desai et al, sheds light on how all of the previous statements may be true and aligns with the general trend of *TNC* expression increasing in the fibroblasts on exposure to ADSC-conditioned media and in the co-culture. Their study focused on its function as an anti-adhesive ECM protein known to modulate cell migration and to trigger loss of focal adhesions, thus signalling the reversal of the myofibroblastic phenotype back into a fibroblast-like state. They believe this to chiefly be regulated by bFGF from ADSCs and that bFGF eventually reverses TNC up-regulation through ERK/MAP Kinase pathway.¹²⁰

Immune modulation, as indicated by the expression profile of CCL19, once again exhibited non-significant changes from a statistical perspective but showed a four-fold decrease in the expression between CCL19 expression in the control chronic RIF diseased fibroblasts and those that were treated with conditioned media. Given that CCL19 can be regarded as a marker of vascular inflammation and its secretion as an attempt to activate both fibroblasts and lymphocytes,⁷⁷ its downregulation by the ADSC secretome is a positive and seemingly fibrosis-modulating finding. No other studies have investigated this in fibrosis. Unfortunately this finding would have to be confirmed in a larger cohort and the exact axis by which the ADSCs are exerting this effect be investigated in further experiments.

Since senescence is a diverse state that varies with cell lineage and stress type and there is no single defining molecular marker, Casella et al. recommend examining multiple senescence markers like p16, p53, p21 and SA- β Gal together and emphasise that while in vitro models of cellular senescence can emulate the phenotypic attributes of senescent cells within tissues and organs, future research efforts will have to examine this differential expression in both physiological and pathological conditions in vivo.¹²¹ By these standards, the fact that not all of the markers were included and this being an in vitro co-culture model may not have been optimal. Neither of the

senescence markers exhibited statistically significant changes or remarkable fold differences in this experiment.

Clinical correlates

In clinical terms, three months post-treatment, patient feedback suggested a perceived improvement in their condition, with many patients quantifying their observed enhancements to be in the range of a 5-15% improvement. That the tissue samples examined in this study were taken from a patient cohort who had shown a positive response to AFG is a notable finding, as it implies that the observed improvement of RIF symptoms in these patients may be attributable to these molecular changes, suggesting a potential predictive value of these markers for treatment responsiveness. These findings, even though they are preliminary, as these outcomes are typically assessed 12-32 months after grafting, rather than at the 3-month mark, are consistent with those of previous studies both from our research group and from other teams, indicating that the majority of treated patients (77.5-97%) experience functional and/or aesthetic improvements and no complications.^{11,19,122}

The statistically non-significant differences in pre and postoperative objective Cutometer measurements could be explained by the fact that the biomechanical properties of the skin are still evolving at this early stage postoperatively, and the sample size was small. However, the overall trend appeared to correlate with the preliminary clinical reports. Naturally, wound healing and tissue remodelling are time-dependent processes, and the biomechanical properties of the skin may continue to change over a longer timescale. Moreover, it is possible that larger sample sizes could reveal more subtle changes that were not detectable in this initial analysis. As such, further studies with much larger cohorts of patients are warranted to confirm these findings and further investigate the potential effects of the treatment on skin biomechanics and patient-reported outcomes.

To further explore these possibilities, future studies should aim to track these parameters longitudinally in the same patients, allowing for the assessment of how these biomechanical properties evolve over time post-operation. Which is actually what the current greater research project is striving to do. Unfortunately, due to the time constraints of this MSc, the majority of this data is not yet available.

Limitations

Some of these limitations have been alluded to briefly above but for clarity will be examined here in greater detail.

Methodological limitations

Flow cytometry is typically utilised together with differentiation assays in stem cell research to confirm the identity of isolated cells.¹²³ This is particularly important in ADSCs given that the stromal vascular fraction contains a number of cell types from pericytes, endothelial and progenitor cells, pre-adipocytes, and hematopoietic cells, with ADSCs only making up roughly 10% of this cell pellet.²⁰ However, in our case, these further steps were not performed due to budgetary constraints. Consequently, this could have an impact on the outcome and interpretations of this research. In order to attempt to mitigate this, the ADSC isolation protocol was strictly adhered to. This protocol has been validated and used by our research group for a number of years.^{83,94,124} Most recently, a paper published just in July 2023 from our team identified that stem cells isolated using the same protocol but from scleroderma patients, expressed cell surface markers CD26, CD73, CD90, and CD34 and “when computing a cell state plot based on adipogenic, vasculogenic, and myogenic differentiation, ADSCs were located in the middle, indicating no commitment to either of these lineages.”⁸³

Another major limitation is that the design of the experiment imposed constraints on assessing all relevant molecular markers, potentially limiting the understanding of the interaction between ADSCs and fibroblasts. The co-culture model employed in this study, despite its utility in examining the interactions between ADSCs and fibroblasts, is an inherently reductionist representation of the complex *in vivo* environment. In the context of RIF, numerous cell types, signalling molecules, and environmental factors interact in a spatially and temporally coordinated manner to mediate the chronic inflammatory response and tissue remodelling.

Specifically, many other cellular players are involved in this story and the order of their activation and their various interactions are incredibly nuanced. For example, inflammasome activation in non-immune cells is thought to typically precede inflammasome activation in immune cells, with the function of immune cells being partly to amplify the inflammatory response at sites of infection

or cellular damage. Interleukin 1 (IL-1), IL-18, transforming growth factor (TGF- α), epidermal growth factor, and fibroblast growth factor (FGF) are some of the important factors that orchestrate wound healing through the secretion of ECM components.³⁸ Similarly, it would have been beneficial to examine the expression of type 3 collagen, as well as that of type 1, as some studies have noted its increased expression in RIF.¹²⁵

Similarly, while we can observe the changes that the fibroblasts have undergone, the paracrine mechanisms of the ADSCs in the context of chronic RIF, or how the ADSCs themselves are changing, are not explored directly by the current experimental setup. This could be key to developing future cell-free therapies in the future. For example, hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) secretion by ADSCs has previously been implicated in multimodal elements of hypertrophic scarring modulation by attenuating macrophage recruitment and activation, suppressing lymphocyte responses, inhibiting collagen synthesis, and recruitment of inherent stem cells to the site.²¹

Moreover, this study only provides a snapshot of the potential effects of ADSCs on fibroblasts at a specific time point (48 hours post co-culture). The dynamic nature of cellular interactions and tissue remodelling in chronic conditions like RIF necessitates understanding these effects at multiple stages over a longer time scale. This could potentially highlight any temporal variations in gene expression, cytokine production, and the resultant impact on extracellular matrix remodelling. Therefore, future investigations employing longer observation periods would provide valuable insights into the dynamic nature of ADSC and fibroblast interactions, even if these may then be more logistically challenging.

Logistical Limitations

A key limitation of the current study is the relatively small sample size (n=3), which could impact the robustness of the results. Future studies with larger sample sizes could help validate these findings. This was a logistical issue that arose as a consequence of the diseased fibroblasts growing very slowly. Furthermore, initially, bulk sequencing analysis was planned to overcome the limitation of targeted molecular assessment. However, due to delayed growth of patient-derived fibroblasts necessary for further co-cultures, this could not be executed within the timeframe of the study. Additionally, the inability to perform additional ELISAs, specifically for pivotal cytokines

such as TGF- β 1, due to unavailability of kits from manufacturers, prevented a more comprehensive investigation of the molecular interplay.

However, the samples for bulk sequencing have been set aside at the time of writing and once more of the slow-growing patient fibroblasts have allowed us to perform further co-cultures we have arranged to send the samples to UCL genomics and will have a much greater dataset to analyse.

The clinical data collection also encountered limitations. Preoperative and postoperative measurements, collected by different individuals, might have introduced a degree of variability, potentially affecting the accuracy of the data. Despite attempts to ensure consistency, the inherent possibility of human error cannot be completely eliminated. Moreover, as was mentioned previously, the results are very preliminary.

Future work

This is very much an emerging field and thus there are many future directions that need to be explored. At the very basic level, as the previous section implies, future studies would certainly benefit from incorporating a broader set of molecular targets, utilising advanced characterization techniques, and standardising clinical data collection procedures.

Collagen-related future experiments

One of the critical areas of interest as a consequence of these findings is the observed increase in procollagen production and its implications on ECM assembly and remodelling in chronic RIF. Understanding this process necessitates an approach that not only quantifies collagen but also characterises its distribution, organisation, and physical properties, as these factors can significantly influence fibrosis. Several experimental approaches could be employed to gain a comprehensive understanding of this complex biological process. Staining techniques, such as Picrosirius Red or immunohistochemistry, could specifically highlight collagen fibres, enabling a comparative analysis of ECM organisation between normal tissues, untreated chronic RIF tissues, and ADSC-treated chronic RIF tissues. Similarly, second harmonic generation imaging could be used to visualise collagen fibres without exogenous labels,¹²⁶ thus providing detailed information about their

organisation and alignment. Additionally, atomic force microscopy could be used to measure the stiffness of tissues,^{127,128} providing a functional readout of how changes in procollagen production might be affecting the ECM. The latter two of these techniques have been utilised previously in liver or lung fibrotic conditions but have not been extensively explored in the skin and could provide novel insights.

Investigating the downstream signalling pathways affected by the changes in collagen production, as well as the cellular responses (e.g., fibroblast activation, immune cell recruitment) associated with these changes, could provide further insights into the effects of ADSCs on ECM remodelling in chronic RIF. This could potentially be done better in animal models, however the practicalities and ethics associated with waiting for acute RIF to turn into chronic RIF in a rodent or minipig model are likely the chief reasons why there are no studies available on this at the time of writing of this thesis.

It is also worth considering that ADSCs themselves could be contributing to the production of procollagen in the experimental conditions. ADSCs, like other mesenchymal stem cells, are known to have the ability to differentiate into various cell types, including fibroblasts, which are the primary producers of collagen in the body. To determine whether ADSCs are indeed producing procollagen, additional experiments could be conducted. In the first instance this could include procollagen ELISA on ADSC-only cultures, immunofluorescence or immunocytochemistry on ADSC-only cultures, and RT-qPCR or Western blot analysis on ADSC-only cultures.

However, more complex techniques could shed more light upon the production changes in the co-cultures. While there is no straightforward way to tag procollagen in live cells to track its origin, indirect methods such as the use of transgenic cells, metabolic labelling, separate culture followed by analysis, single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq), or cell-sorting followed by gene or protein analysis could be employed.

In particular, transgenic animal models or cells that produce fluorescently tagged proteins have been used to track protein synthesis in real-time.¹²⁹ In this case, the development of transgenic ADSCs that express a fluorescently tagged procollagen could provide crucial insights into whether the ADSCs themselves contribute to the increased production. Observing the presence or absence of fluorescently tagged procollagen in the co-culture system could confirm or refute this possibility.

However, naturally this would be quite challenging to execute and would necessitate familiarity and training with the technique beforehand.

The metabolic labelling approach is another similar potential strategy. Non-radioactive isotopic labelling methods involving stable isotopes (e.g., ^{13}C , ^{15}N , ^{18}O , or ^2H), known as stable isotope labelling by amino acids in cell culture (SILAC), can be used to analyse protein synthesis, turnover, and modification.¹³⁰ Another metabolic labelling technique involves incorporating azido- or alkyne- labelled amino acids into newly synthesised proteins, which can then be detected using click chemistry.^{131,132} The major advantage of this approach would be that these reactions are bio-orthogonal: with neither the reactants nor their product's functional groups interacting with functionalized biomolecules. Additionally, the reactions are able to proceed in aqueous solution and at room temperature.¹³² Specifically for collagen, isotopically labelled proline could be used, as proline residues make up a significant proportion of the collagen triple helix.¹³³

These labelled residues could then be tracked and quantified, providing a clear picture of whether the ADSCs are producing procollagen directly or influencing fibroblast procollagen production indirectly.

Future potential avenues related to TGF- β

There are many additional possible molecular avenues to explore and not all of these can be covered in this work; however, a notable possible experimental target is that of another important member of the TGF- β subfamily. TGF- β 3 is the predominant isoform present in prenatal life and has been linked to scarless healing in the foetus, and a decrease in scar formation without a reduction in scar tensile strength in adult wound healing.¹¹⁰ Changing the TGF- β 1/TGF- β 3 ratio towards an increase in TGF- β 3 seems to reduce scarring¹³⁴ and an increase in TGF- β 3 expression has been observed after stem cell treatment in both in vitro and in vivo models, suggesting its potential role in antifibrotic therapy reiterating.^{106,135} Thus, future in vitro studies exploring the role of TGF- β 3 in ADSC-mediated fibrosis treatment could be fruitful.

Bench to bedside: eventually developing therapeutics targeting these mechanisms

Treating RIF is challenging, with existing non-operative strategies offering limited effectiveness. These include corticosteroids for inflammation; physiotherapy for contracture mitigation; pentoxifylline, vitamin E, and *N*-acetyl-L-cysteine for combating oxidative stress; superoxide dismutase for TGF- β regulation; hyperbaric oxygen for pain and swelling reduction, and laser therapy.^{97,136} Unfortunately, these have proven suboptimal. Conversely, fat grafting can add bulk to facial areas impacted by RIF, cover small defects, assist in major reconstructions, or replace more invasive procedures for patients unsuitable for microvascular reconstruction. Furthermore, it can help soften and prepare fibrotic skin for surgery, enhancing its healing capacity.⁹⁷ However even though it is minimally invasive, not all patients are suitable for fat transfer. Or alternatively, even when fat grafting is used, some emerging therapeutics could potentially reduce graft resorption and improve healing.

It is quite safe to say that there is a pressing need to develop novel treatment strategies for chronic RIF, particularly of the head and neck, as this area is so visible and functionally important to patient's quality of life.

Both novel cell-based and cell-free therapies involving ADSCs are an emerging frontier in chronic RIF treatment.¹³⁷ ADSCs, with their multilineage differentiation potential, robust proliferative capacity, and immunomodulatory properties, could be harnessed to counteract the fibrotic changes and restore functionality to affected tissues.²

However, as our understanding of the molecular and cellular interactions underpinning these processes remains incomplete, more studies like this one are needed to elucidate these modulatory mechanisms further and could open up other potential avenues to explore.

In theory, in cell-based therapies, ADSCs could be harvested, expanded *in vitro*, and subsequently injected into the fibrotic areas. This could help to attenuate the fibrotic response, stimulate tissue regeneration, and reduce inflammation. However, there are many real-world concerns and challenges to this approach. One of the primary concerns is ensuring the safety of the patient, as manipulating cells *in vitro* could potentially lead to unwanted changes. For instance, prolonged cell culture can sometimes lead to genetic instability or transformation of the cells, which could potentially increase the risk of tumorigenesis when these cells are reintroduced into the body.¹³⁸ In

addition, there is the potential for contamination with bacteria, fungi, or viruses during the in vitro expansion process, which could cause infections upon reinjection.¹³⁹

Another concern is about the effectiveness of the therapy. After reintroduction into the body, the injected cells must survive, integrate into the host tissue, and function properly. However, many transplanted cells often do not survive long-term or may not function as intended.¹⁴⁰

There are also logistical and regulatory challenges. Navigating the regulatory landscape is crucial to bringing these therapies from the bench to the bedside. For instance, expanding cells in vitro to the numbers required for therapy is costly and time-consuming. Additionally, as these therapies are considered advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs), they are subject to stringent regulations by bodies like the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), European Medicines Agency (EMA), and Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA). In the United States, the FDA regulates ATMPs under the umbrella of human cells, tissues, and cellular and tissue-based products (HCT/Ps) with detailed guidelines on the regulatory process. FDA regulations encompass donor eligibility, current good tissue practice (cGTP), and current good manufacturing practice (cGMP), with recent efforts to streamline the process for ATMP approval, although challenges remain.^{141,142}

The European Union's EMA has provided comprehensive guidelines since 2007, encapsulated in Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007. However, differences in the interpretation and implementation of these guidelines across member states, plus the high cost and complexity of the centralised approval process, have presented significant barriers to ATMP development and commercialisation.¹⁴³

Meanwhile, in the UK, Brexit has added an extra layer of complexity, with the MHRA establishing an independent regulatory framework whilst maintaining alignment with the EMA's guidelines. However, the uncertainties arising from this transition sometimes pose additional challenges for developers.¹⁴⁴ Successful navigation through these complex regulatory pathways necessitates robust preclinical and clinical data demonstrating safety, efficacy, and quality.

On the other hand, cell-free therapies based upon our understanding of the regenerative mechanisms could hold much promise and avoid many of the challenges associated with cell-based treatments.¹⁴⁵ These therapeutics could include existing drugs, like the iron chelator deferoxamine, which when injected into the area prior to fat transfer has been noted to optimise the skin, as it is thought to possess antioxidant properties, thus reducing reactive oxygen species locally.⁴⁸

Alternatively, these therapeutics could be completely novel drugs. A notable avenue being explored

is that of administration of TGF- β inhibitors.¹⁴⁶ However, thus far this has not moved beyond mice models and like many of the RIF-focused animal studies, this mitigating effect has only been demonstrated in what is inherently acute fibrosis.

A number of advanced bioengineering strategies have also been suggested. For example, 3D bioprinting could be used to fabricate personalised ADSCs-laden grafts, providing both a source of healthy cells and a supportive ECM-like scaffold to promote tissue regeneration.¹⁴⁷ Alternatively, biomimetic hydrogels could act as delivery vehicles for ADSCs or their exosomes,¹⁴⁸ enabling controlled and sustained release of the therapeutic agents at the site of fibrosis.¹⁴⁹ However, these experimental bioengineering solutions could pose even greater regulatory challenges, in addition to those of characterisation, quality control, and standardisation of the therapeutic products, as well as ensuring patient safety through rigorous monitoring of adverse effects.

Wherever the future leads, establishing robust protocols and safety measures will be vital to securing regulatory approval and ensuring the successful clinical translation of these therapies.

Conclusions

This study illuminates the pivotal role of ADSCs in modifying the gene expression profile of fibroblasts derived from chronic RIF tissues, affirming the emergent perception of ADSCs as key facilitators of tissue regeneration and repair.

One notable observation was the significant reduction in *COL1A1* gene expression, a marker of type I collagen, in RIF fibroblasts following exposure to ADSCs. This suggests the potential of ADSCs to mitigate the excess collagen accumulation typical of fibrotic disorders. Paradoxically, despite this decrease in gene expression, an increase in procollagen production was observed, indicating the complex and intricate regulatory role of ADSCs in ECM remodelling.

Furthermore, the study identified trends suggestive of ADSCs' involvement in modulating TGF- β /Smad axis, an essential element of the fibrotic process, and *MMP9*, a critical matrix metalloproteinase responsible for ECM degradation and remodelling. However, these trends were not statistically significant, necessitating further validation in larger cohorts.

Interestingly, ADSCs seemed to increase the expression of TNC, an ECM glycoprotein involved in tissue repair and regeneration, even though the upregulation was not statistically significant. This observation warrants further investigation, as *TNC* modulation may play a critical role in reversing fibrosis.

The study also explored the potential immune modulatory and anti-senescent properties of ADSCs, as indicated by the expression profiles of *CCL19*, *CDKN1A*, and *CDKN2A*. However, no significant changes were found, possibly due to the limitations of the in vitro model used.

Three months post-treatment, patients from whom the tissue samples were taken reported perceived improvement in their condition, confirming their status as positive responders to ADSC treatment. While no statistically significant differences were observed in pre and postoperative objective Cutometer measurements, this could indicate the need for a more extended observation period and larger sample size to understand the precise effects of ADSCs on tissue properties. In particular, the understanding that the studied tissues come from clinical responders could serve as a starting point for future studies aimed at identifying predictive markers for treatment success.

This study contributes to understanding the role of ADSCs in managing chronic RIF and reveals the need for deeper exploration of their therapeutic potential. The nuances of ADSC-mediated modulation, its impact on various molecular markers, and the implications for patient outcomes, signal a compelling direction for future research. Subsequent studies should focus on validating these preliminary findings in larger cohorts, and further investigate the role of ADSCs in immune response modulation, cellular senescence, and tissue repair processes.

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Appendix

Appendix table 1: Review of clinical studies

Author	Study Design	Level of evidence	No of patients	M:F ratio	Cancer location	Concurrent Surgery	Indication for AFG	AFG Technique	ADSC enrichment	AFG Adjunctive procedures	Volume of AFG injected (/treatment)	No. of AFG treatments (/patient)	Outcome
Bamba et al. (2021)	Prospective case series	IV	9	8:1	Oropharynx = 3, Tonsils = 2, Base of tongue = 3, Thyroid = 1	Not reported	Xerostomia	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	Not reported	3-4ml per site (mean); no measure of spread stated	1.4 (mean) (range 1-4)	improvement in xerostomia symptoms with AFT alone
Griffin et al. (2019)	Retrospective cohort study	IIB	38	22:16	Mandible (45% primary bone neoplasm), floor of the mouth (7.9%), buccal mucosa (2.6%), maxillary mucosa or maxillary antrum (10.5%), nose, cheek, nasolabial fold, or zygomatic region (13.2%), submandibular or parotid gland (10.5%)	Composite mandibular free flap reconstruction = 20 (17 had composite free fibula flap, 3 scapula and deep circumflex iliac artery flap); dual flap reconstruction with fibula and radial forearm flap = 1	Contouring, volume restoration after an ablative procedure, RIF	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	Not reported	12.52ml ±4.63ml (mean ±SD)	1.9 (mean) (range 1-6)	97% reported esthetic and functional improvements in their RIF and volumetric defect at follow-up of 32 months. 63% major and 34% minor improvements without causing any complications
Karmali et al. (2018)	Prospective case series	IV	81 (69% of the 116 patient cohort received radiotherapy)	Not reported	Head and neck reconstruction cases; no other specific information	Seventy-six patients (66 percent) underwent some form of free flap reconstruction for a defect caused by oncologic surgery, whereas 40 patients (34 percent) had no flap and only received autologous fat grafting for reconstruction	Head and neck reconstruction; as an adjunct to improve aesthetic outcomes, RIF	Coleman microinjection system, no centrifugation (mentor Worldwide, LLC, Santa Barbara, California, USA); Cytori PureGraft System (Cytori Therapeutics Inc, San Diego, California, USA); Revolve System (LifeCell Corp, Bridgewater, New Jersey, USA)	None	Seventy-six patients (66%) underwent some form of free flap reconstruction for a defect caused by oncologic surgery, whereas 40 patients (34%) had no flap and only received autologous fat grafting for reconstruction.	24.8 ±20.2ml (mean ±SD)	1.6±1 (mean ±SD) (range 1-6)	Complications occurred in 6%, none of which required a return to theatre or readmission. Aesthetic analysis revealed that both plastic surgeons and laypersons thought patients appeared closer to normal following AFT

Gutiérrez Santamaría et al. (2017)	Prospective case series	IV	12	Not reported	Oral cavity = 10, oral and zygomatic = 1, minor salivary gland = 1	Segmentary mandibulectomy, neck dissection fibula free-flap reconstruction = 8, segmental mandibulectomy without reconstruction = 1; hard palate resection with a forearm free flap = 1; hemimaxillectomy and temporalis muscle pedicled flap reconstruction = 1, malar tumour excision = 1	RIF, volume restoration, neck mobility issues, chewing, deglutition and oronasal fistula	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	Not reported	23.9 ml (mean) (range 5-70ml)	1	83% and 92% aesthetic and functional improvement respectively
Kraaijenka et al. (2016)	Prospective case series	IV	4	1:0	Base of tongue = 1, tonsil = 2, oral cavity = 1	Not reported	Dysphagia and dysphonia	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	2 patients had surgical resections as well as radiotherapy	26.2ml (mean) (range 11-34.5ml)	2-3 (range)	potential value for improving swallowing function: Two out of five patients treated with three lipofiling sessions were no longer feeding tube dependent
Tarallo et al. (2012)	Case report	V	1	0:1	Right lower eyelid	None	Severe grade 3 cicatricial ectropion	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	Right lateral tarsal strip canthoplasty	5ml	1	Skin texture, softness, and elasticity improved with further symmetrization.
Navach et al. (2011)	Case report	V	1	1:0	Not reported	Submental lymphadenectomy	Dysphagia	Coleman technique, centrifugation not specified	None	None	5ml, 3.5ml on the left and 1.5ml on the right	1	successfully used to improve abnormal swallowing
Belyea et al. (2010)	Case report	V	1	1:0	Lower lip	Wedge resection = 2 and functional neck dissection = 1	Contouring and the whistle deformity	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	Otoplasty, liposuction, hair microimplants,	35.9ml (mean) (range 6-55ml)	2 (mean) (range 1-3)	AFG appears to be a viable option for correcting a whistle deformity
Faghahati et al. (2010)	Retrospective case series	IV	4	2:2	Nasopharynx = 2, orbit = 1, pterygoid = 1	None	Craniofacial asymmetry	Coleman technique, manual aspiration, centrifugation, No washing	None	None	25ml (mean) (range 15-30ml)	3.9 (mean)	Cosmetic results were considered satisfactory by both the patient and the surgeon in all four cases

Kim et al. (2010)	Retrospective case series	IV	6	4:2	Orbit	Surgical ablation = 2, resection = 4, all had enucleation	RIF, unable to fit orbital prosthesis	Coleman technique, centrifugation not specified	None	Hyaluronic acid-based tissue filler	Three treatments, first 4.5ml then 5ml then 3ml	3	After serial fat grafting, four of the six patients could successfully be fitted for orbital prostheses.
Phulpin et al. (2009)	Retrospective case series	IV	11	7:4	Submaxillary gland and thyroid = 1, larynx = 2, retromolar = 1, floor of mouth = 2, oropharynx = 1, nasal cavity = 1, tongue = 1, soft palate = 1, salivary gland = 1	Submandibular laryngectomy = 1, laryngectomy = 3, mandibular resection = 2, oropharyngeal resection = 2, nasal resection = 1, palatal resection = 1, partial resection of oral cavity = 1	Aesthetic, contouring, RIF, limited head and neck mobility, swallowing/chewing difficulty, larynx mobility, tongue volume deficit, soft palate deficit	Coleman technique, no centrifugation, No washing	None	20 sessions of massage of the graft areas	48.9ml (mean) in total	2.2 (mean), (range 1-5)	10/11 patients aesthetic and functional rehabilitation
Klinger et al. (2008)	Retrospective case series	IV	3	2:1	Orbit	Enucleation	RIF, socket too small for an implant, pain	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	None	5ml, no measure of spread reported	Not reported	clinical appearance and subjective patient feelings after a 6-month follow-up period suggest considerable improvement in the mimic features, skin texture, and thickness.
Coleman et al. (2006)	Case report	V	1	1:0	Masseter	Radial masseter resection	Volume restoration	Coleman technique, centrifugation	None	None	115ml	1	Observation over time demonstrates more than just filling of the scars. Not only provides a structural improvement in a remarkable bone and soft-tissue deficiency but also results in an improvement in the quality of skin damaged by radiation and in the recovery of beard hair follicles.

Appendix table 2: Review of in vitro studies

Paper	Intervention preparation	ADSC characterisation	Other cell types	Disease model	Radiation protocol	Outcomes	End-point(s)	Results	Conclusions
Haubner et al. (2013)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 5/6	Details not provided	HDMEC	Intervention: HDMEC/ADSC direct co-culture in endothelial cell growth medium (irradiated) Controls: 1.HDMEC/medium (irradiated); 2.ADSC/medium (irradiated); 3.HDMEC/ADSC (non-irradiated)	Single exposure of 2, 6 and 12Gy	Cell viability (Cedex XS Analyzer System) Cytokine production (ELISA: ICAM, VCAM-1, IL-6, FGF)	48h post-radiation 48h post-radiation	ICAM-1, VCAM-1, IL-6 and FGF secretion significantly lower in HDMEC/ADSC co-culture compared to controls	Radiation-induced endothelial cell dysfunction may be mitigated by ADSCs through decreased expression of pro-atherogenic adhesion molecules
Shukla et al. (2020)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSC-CM collected after 72h of culture	Not applicable	NHDF	Intervention: ADSC-CM/ NHDF (irradiated) Controls: 1.NHDF alone (non-irradiated); 2.NHDF/control media (irradiated)	Single exposure of 10Gy	Gap closure (scratch migration assay)	48h post-radiation	17.5% reduction in NHDF migration after ADSC-CM treatment	ADSC-CM reversed dysregulated NHDF hypermigration post-radiation
Haubner et al. (2015)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 5/6	Details not provided	NHDF	Intervention: NHDF/ADSC direct co-culture in fibroblast growth medium (irradiated) Controls: 1.ADSC alone (irradiated); 2.NHDF alone (irradiated); 3.NHDF/ADSC (non-irradiated)	Single exposure of 2, 6 and 12Gy	Cell proliferation (BrdU colorimetric assay) Gene expression/proteomic profile (RT-qPCR: MMP1, MMP2, MMP13; ELISA: TGF-β1, TIMP1 and TIMP2)	48h post-radiation 48h post-radiation	Increased MMP1 and MMP2 expression in irradiated NHDF/ADSC co-culture Increased secretion of TIMP1 and TIMP2 in irradiated NHDF/ADSC co-culture	ADSC-induced increased MMP1 expression may stimulate neovascularization and fibroblast migration The balance of MMPs and TIMPs may be altered by ADSCs to regulate repair
Yao et al. (2021)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of rat adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 3 and supernatant derived	Flow cytometry (CD10, CD34, CD45, CD73, CD90, and CD105)	HaCat NOK	Intervention: HaCaT/NOK/ADSC culture-supernatant (irradiated) Control: HaCaT/NOK/normal culture medium (irradiated)	Single exposure of 5 and 20Gy	Cell apoptosis (TUNEL assay) Proteomic profile (Western Blotting: CTSF, Bid, BAX and Caspase-9)	72h post-radiation 72h post-radiation	Lower cell apoptosis rates and downregulated CTSF, BAX, Bid, and Caspase-9 secretion in the culture supernatant-treated group	ADSC-culture supernatant markedly attenuated radiation-induced apoptosis by downregulating CTSF and downstream pro-apoptotic proteins, and upregulating anti-apoptotic proteins.

Ejaz et al. (2019)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of human subcutaneous white adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 4	Details not provided	HFF	Intervention: transwell HFF/ADSC co-culture (irradiated, ADSCs added 24h post-irradiation and co-culture maintained for 48h) Controls: 1.HFF (non-irradiated); 2.HFF/ADSC (non-irradiated)	Single exposure of 10Gy	Fibrosis-associated gene expression (RT-qPCR: TGF- β 1, CTGF, NK-kB, IL-1, Col1-Col6, TNF and HGF) Proteomic profile (Luminex assay and western blotting: HGF)	72h post-radiation 72h post-radiation	Downregulation in the expression of fibrosis-associated genes and increased HGF production in irradiated HFF/ADSC co-culture	HGF production by ADSCs may mediate anti-fibrotic effects through down-regulation of fibrosis associated genes and bone marrow cell migration
Xiao et al. (2020)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of human subcutaneous white adipose tissue Mature adipocytes collected	Not applicable	HaCaT WS1	Intervention: transwell mature adipocyte/HaCaT/WS1 co-culture (irradiated) Controls: 1.WS1 (irradiated); 2.HaCaT (irradiated) Sub-experiments: 1.HaCaT incubated with fresh medium containing EGFP-tagged FABP4 protein; 2.PA incubated with WS1	Single exposure of 5 and 20Gy	Cell migration assay Cell proliferation assay Cell cycle analysis	24h post-radiation 24h post-radiation 24h post-radiation	Adipocytes increased fibroblast migration, but did not increase proliferation of co-cultured HaCat and WS1 FABP4 reduced radiation-induced DNA damage, whilst PA independently promoted migration of irradiated cells	Adipocytes facilitate the migration and repair of irradiated fibroblasts possibly through fatty acids (PA) and FABP4
Saijo et al. (2019)	Source of ADSCs not provided ADSCs cultured to passage 4-6, with ADSC-CM obtained after culture	Details not provided	HDLEC	Interventions: HDLEC/ADSC and HDLEC/ADSC/ADSC-CM co-cultures (irradiated) Controls: 1.HDLEC monoculture (irradiated); 2.ADSC-CM (irradiated); 3.HDLEC/ADSC-CM (non-irradiated)	Single exposure of 1,2 6, or 12Gy	Cell proliferation (DAPI assay) Cell migration (scratch assay) Tube formation assay Proteomic profile (ELISA: bFGF, HGF, IGF-1, VEGF-A, VEGF-C, and Western Blotting: bFGF, VEGF-A, VEGF-C)	120h post-radiation 12h post-radiation 12h post-radiation 168h post-radiation	ADSCs reversed radiation-induced suppression of Human Dermal Lymphatic Endothelial Cells proliferation, potentially through lymphangiogenic factor upregulation (bFGF in particular) Addition of ADSC-CM resulted in significantly smaller scratches and approximately two-fold longer tubes	ADSC-CM and ADSCs show similar effects on the lymphangiogenic ability of HDLEC (increased proliferation, migration, and tube formation)

Yu et al. (2021)	Collagenase digestion, filtration, and centrifugation of human white adipose tissue Supernatants and adipocytes discarded, and SVF obtained	Flow cytometry (CD29, CD11b, CD73, CD45, CD105, CD90, CD34, HLA-D)	WS1	Intervention: WS1/SVF transwell co-culture (irradiated) Control: WS1 monoculture (irradiated)	Single exposure of 5Gy	Proteomic profile (TMT based proteomic quantification) Further GO annotation of proteome and KEGG pathway analysis	48h post-radiation	Upregulated proteins included DMTF1, MFAP5, P116, MMP-1 and collagen chains KEGG-based pathway enrichment analysis significant upregulation of ECM-receptor interaction and focal adhesion pathways	SVF altered the fibroblast proteomic profile, further research is required to investigate significance.
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Appendix table 3: Summary of in vivo animal studies

Paper	Intervention preparation	Disease model	Radiation protocol	Outcomes	Endpoint	Results	Conclusions
Borrelli et al. (2020)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 3	Mice (n=20) grafted 4wk post-radiation Interventions (ADSCs): 1. CD74+; 2. CD74-; 3. unsorted Control: lipoaspirate only	30Gy fractionated into six 5Gy doses on alternate days (total=12 days)	Fat retention (Micro CT) Mechanical strength testing (Microtester) Histology (H&E) IHC (versican, elastin and fibrillin) FACS (fibroblast subpopulations)	8 wk post-graft	CD74+ ADSC enriched group showed greater integrity, reduced inflammation and fibrosis, decreased collagen and versican staining, and decreased proportion of fibrotic papillary and reticular fibroblasts, but significantly increased proportions of more anti-fibrotic zigzag and lipofibroblasts	Fat grafts enriched with CD74+ ADSCs showed improved histological quality, decreased pro-fibrotic protein production, and influenced fibroblast sub-populations
Sultan et al. (2012)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue Whole fat obtained	Mice (n=25) Interventions: 1. Irradiated/ whole fat graft; 2. Irradiated/ sham graft (saline) Control: non-irradiated	45Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E) IHC (CD31 and Smad3) Scar index (Picosirius red staining for collagen)	4 and 8 wk post-graft	Fat-grafted mice showed reduced hyperpigmentation, ulceration, epidermal thickness (2.6x), scar index, CD31 and Smad3 (pro-fibrotic marker) staining compared to sham- and control groups	Fat grafting slows fibrosis progression perhaps by reducing microvascular damage, but no mechanistic conclusions can be derived
Forcheon et al. (2012)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of minipig adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 3-8	Minipigs (n=13) grafted post-radiation Intervention: ADSC graft (50x10 ⁶ cells x4 over 3mo) Control: PBS injection	51Gy single exposure	Clinical score (pathological signs and pain evaluation) IHC (vWF and cytokeratin) Histology (H&E) ADSC movement (Q-dot and labelling)	140 days post-graft	Intervention group showed complete epidermal recovery (cytokeratin), and earlier lymphocyte infiltration into the dermis with greater vascularization (vWF) Grafted ADSCs were localised at dermis/ subcutis barrier but not the epidermis	Owing to lymphocyte co-localization, ADSCs could potentially attract immune cells via paracrine mechanisms No evidence of ADSC differentiation into keratinocytes
Riccobono et al. (2018)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of minipig adipose tissue (autologous) and two other animals (allogeneic) ADSCs cultured to passage 2	Minipigs (n=18) grafted post-radiation Interventions: 1. autologous ADSCs; 2. allogeneic ADSCs (50x10 ⁶ cells x4 over 3mo) Control: PBS injection	50.6Gy ± 4.1Gy single exposure	Clinical score (pathological signs and pain evaluation)	119-124 days post-radiation	Final clinical score of autologous ADSC-grafted intervention group significantly improved compared to control group (less erythema, induration, oedema etc.) No significant difference in clinical score between allogeneic ADSC intervention group and control group	Autologous ADSCs improved healing of radiation wounds, but reason for failure of allogeneic ADSCs is unclear Inflammation profile of both ADSC subtypes should be explored further
Garza et al. (2014)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue Whole fat obtained	Mice (n=9) Intervention: irradiated/ whole fat graft Control: non-irradiated/ whole fat graft	30 Gy fractionated into 6 fractions of 5Gy (total=12 days)	Collagen staining (Picosirius red) IHC (CD31) Histology (H&E)	8wk post-graft	Lower levels of collagen and increased vascular density (CD31) in fat-grafted irradiated tissue compared to pre-graft irradiated tissue At 2wk, irradiated mice demonstrated significant dermal thinning compared to control, extending to 8wk Lower graft retention in irradiated group, but similar quality of remaining fat to control	AFTs may contribute to improved skin quality through neoangiogenesis, reduced collagen deposition and reduced dermal thickness

Riccobono et al. (2016)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of minipig adipose tissue ADSCs grown to 85-95% confluence, proportion transfected with Shh plasmid	Minipigs (n=14) grafted post-radiation Interventions: 1. autologous ADSC; 2. ShhADSC (50x10 ⁶ cells x4 over 3mo) Control: PBS-injection	50.6 ± 4.1Gy single exposure	Clinical score (pathological signs and pain evaluation) *Autologous ADSC and PBS control groups are historical results	55-92 days post-radiation	Shh-ADSC injections well-tolerated, with clinical benefit (skin repair and pain decrease) similar to autologous ADSC group	Shh gene therapy initially hypothesised to enrich secretome and improve cell proliferation and neoangiogenesis, but no added clinical benefit seen
Luan et al. (2016)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSCs harvested for CAL, and fat centrifuged for grafting	Mice (n=unknown) Interventions: 1. CAL/irradiated; 2. Fat graft/irradiated Controls: 1. CAL/non-irradiated; 2. Fat graft/non-irradiated	30Gy fractionated into 6 doses of 5 Gy, (total=12 days)	Fat graft retention volume (micro CT) IHC (CD31) Histology (H&E) Tensile stress strength (Force transducer)	8wk post-graft	The CAL/irradiated group showed significantly reduced dermal thickness and collagen content, and improved skin vascularity and stiffness in comparison to the fat/irradiated group Measures were comparable to non-irradiated controls	CAL-treated mice showed improved pathological markers, providing evidence for ADSC enrichment of fat grafts
Ejaz et al. (2019)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of GFP+/Luc+ mice adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 4	Mice (n=unknown) grafted post-radiation Intervention: ADSCs (injected into hind limbs) Control: saline injection	35Gy single exposure	Leg movement (protractor) Collagen staining (Masson's trichrome) Histology (H&E) ADSC tracking (GFP+/Luc+ expression)	28 days post-radiation 50 days post-radiation 77 days post-radiation	ADSC-treated mice showed improved limb movement, and reduced epithelial thickness and collagen density compared to control Positive luciferase signals seen at day 77 post-ADSC injection	ADSCs injected at irradiated sites persist and coupled with the in-vitro results of increased HGF production, suggest a local paracrine mechanism
Lindgren et al. (2019)	Whole fat obtained from breasts of female patients with treated breast cancer (surgery + adjuvant radiotherapy)	Female patients (n=30) Intervention: whole fat/irradiated Control: non-irradiated/nil graft (contralateral breast of same patients)	Adjuvant radiotherapy given at least 12 months prior to patient recruitment (dose not provided)	Gene expression analysis (microarrays) IHC (CD86)	12mo post-graft	19.2% of the 3000 genes evaluated had significantly less variation in expression between the respective sides after AFT than before AFT Macrophage ratio (CD86) in irradiated vs. non-irradiated breast lower after AFT	AFT suppresses pathways involved in inflammation (IFN- γ response), fibrosis and hypoxia even a year post-radiation exposure
Bertrand et al. (2021)	Human adipose tissue grafts from healthy 35-year-old female, (Microfat (MF) + SVF isolated through collagenase digestion, PRP from blood sample)	Mice (n=45) Interventions (irradiated): 1. MF alone; 2. MF/SVF; 3. MF/PRP; 4. Ringer's lactate Control: non-irradiated	60Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E) Collagen density (Masson's trichrome and orcein staining) Vascularisation (number and diameter of dermal capillaries)	12wk post-graft	Greatest area of wound healing seen in MF+ PRP group No significant difference in epidermal thickness amongst the cell-based intervention groups. MF+SVF group showed the greatest increase in density and diameter of vessels	Combination therapies appear to be more effective than SVF or MF alone, likely through increased vascularisation and decreased subcutaneous sclerosis

Borelli et al. (2020)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue Whole fat and SVC isolated	Mice (n=4) grafted post-radiation Interventions: 1. Whole fat/ SVC; 2. Whole fat only; 3. PBS injection Control: sham (no injection)	30Gy fractionated into 6 doses of 5Gy (total=12 days)	Limb extension (ruler) Tensile strength testing (microtester) Histology (H&E) Collagen density (Masson's Trichrome, and Picrosirius Red) IF (CD31, CD26, Dlk-1, vimentin)	12wk post-graft	Greatest reduction in skin stiffness (less dense collagen) and greatest increase in elasticity in whole fat/SVC group Greatest increase in whole fat/SVC group (CD31) Significantly fewer CD26- and Dlk-1-positive fibroblasts in fat-grafted mice relative to control	The greatest functional and histological benefits were observed in mice receiving fat enriched with SVC
Deleon et al. (2021)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSCs cultured (passage details not provided)	Mice (n=20) grafted post-radiation Interventions: 1. CD146+ ADSCs; 2. CD146- ADSCs; 3. unfractionated ADSCs Control: fat only	30Gy fractionated into 6 doses of 5Gy given on alternate days (total=12 days)	Fat graft volume (Micro CT) Mechanical strength testing (microtester) Histology (H&E) Collagen staining (Masson's trichrome) IF (CD31, TGF- β , fibrillin, elastin, perilipin)	8wk post-graft	CD146+ADSC-enriched fat graft group showed significantly more live adipocytes (perilipin) and vasculature (CD31), and showed the least collagen and TGF- β 1 staining CD31+ enriched graft group showed the greatest improvement in skin elasticity (fibrillin and elastin)	The CD146+ ADSC subset comprises 1/3 of SVF, and may be responsible for the clinical effects observed with fat grafting in RIF
Yao et al. (2021)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of rat adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 3	Rats (n=48) grafted post-radiation Intervention: ADSCs Control: PBS-injection	90Gy single exposure	Histology (H &E) Collagen staining (Masson's trichrome and hydroxyproline) IHC (BCL2, CTSF, BAX) Western Blotting (CTSF, BAX, Bcl-xL, Caspase 9, GAPDH) Cell apoptosis (TUNEL assay)	12wk post graft	Significantly lower lymphocyte count, collagen proportion and apoptotic cell count in ADSC-graft group compared to control Improved sebaceous gland and hair follicle regeneration in ADSC-graft group Expression of pro-apoptotic proteins significantly lower in ADSC-graft group relative to control	ADSCs inhibited lymphocyte migration, cell apoptosis and fibrosis formation In addition, gross skin histology was improved
Khademi et al. (2019)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of rat adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 3	Rats (n=32) grafted post-radiation Intervention: ADSCs Control: PBS injection	30Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E)	4wk post-graft	There were no significant differences in angiogenesis, fibrosis, collagen level, macrophage count, and epithelisation between the intervention and control groups Greater wound healing observed in intervention group	Lone ADSCs may not have an impact on alleviating RIF, and may require augmentation with PRP
Riccobono et al. ()	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of minipig adipose tissue Autologous ADSCs cultured (passage details not provided)	Minipigs (n=6) grafted post-radiation Intervention: autologous ADSCs (intra-dermal and intramuscular injections) Control: PBS-injection	50.6 \pm 4.1Gy single exposure	Western blotting (IL-6, IL-1 β , IL-10) In-situ hybridization (TGF- β 1, β -actin) IF (CD206/vWF, CD68 /CD206, CD80/CD206)	76 days post-radiation	TGF- β 1 significantly increased in ADSC group, IL-10 detected only in ADSC group, and IL-6 and IL-1 β not detected in either Lower number of M1 macrophages (CD68, CD80) in ADSC group compared to control M2 macrophages (CD206) detected only in ADSC group	ADSCs may promote M2 macrophage polarisation, likely through IL-10 and TGF- β 1 upregulation

Riccobono et al. ()	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of minipig adipose tissue Autologous ADSCs cultured	Minipigs (n=6) Intervention: 1. Irradiated/ autologous ADSCs (intradermal and intramuscular injections) Control: 1. Irradiated/ PBS-injection; 2. Non-irradiated	50.6 ± 4.1Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E) IHC (α -SMA, collagen 1 and 3) Western blotting (IL-6, IL-1 β , IL-10, SCA1, Pax7, Myf5, MyoD)	76 days post-radiation	IL-10 detected only in ADSC group, and IL-6 and IL-1 β not detected in either Two-fold greater intensity of quiescent satellite cell marker Pax7 in ADSC-treated animals in comparison to corresponding nonirradiated tissue Myf5 (overexpressed in activated satellite cells) was detected in all samples	ADSCs may promote M2 polarization through secretion of IL10 ADSCs may aid tissue repair through quiescent satellite cell recruitment and activation.
Sun et al. (2015)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of rabbit adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage 3	Rabbits (n=64) Intervention (intramuscular): Irradiated/ ADSC-graft Controls (intramuscular): 1. Irradiated/ PBS-injection; 2. Non-irradiated contralateral body sides of ADSC- and PBS-injected rabbits	80Gy single exposure	Collagen staining (Masson's trichome) IHC (TGF- β 1) Western blotting (TGF- β 1) ADSC tracking (CM-Dil label)	26wk post-radiation	Significant decrease in collagen level and TGF- β 1 expression in ADSC-treated group relative to control ADSCs dispersed into surrounding muscular tissue with time	In irradiated muscle, ADSCs could alleviate RIF by suppressing TGF- β 1 expression Further research in TGF- β 1 knockout models is warranted
Huang et al. (2022)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of rat adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passages 4-6	Rats (n=16) grafted post-radiation Intervention: ADSCs Control: PBS-injection	50Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E) IF (vWF, CD31) ADSC tracking (CM-Dil label)	6wk post-radiation 2wk post-radiation	Capillary density (CD31, vWF) and thickness in the dermis were increased in the ADSC-treated group compared to control ADSCs co-localised with Ki67 (cell proliferation marker), CD31 and vWF At 2wk, ADSCs were clustered at the site of the injection but did not disperse into surrounding tissue	ADSCs could increase tissue survival and vasculature in RIF (either by fusing with or differentiating into vascular endothelial cells) Extended follow-up of CM-Dil labelled ADSCs required to track migration
Chen et al. (2014)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of minipig adipose tissue Autologous ADSCs cultured to passage 3-5 PRF obtained from minipig blood sample	Minipigs (n=20) grafted post-radiation Interventions: 1. autologous ADSCs; 2. PRF; 3. ADSCs/PRF Control: PBS-injection	20Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E) IHC (Factor VIII) Cell apoptosis (TUNEL assay)	6mo post-final injection	The ADSCs/PRF combination group showed the highest adipocyte count and vascular density, as well as the lowest apoptotic density and fibrosis- and inflammation-associated characteristics. These differences relative to other groups were statistically significant	ADSC and PRF mixture achieved even better soft tissue regeneration than ADSCs or PRF alone Both may have similar mechanisms of action (neovascularisation, anti-apoptosis, structural remodelling)

Evin et al. (2021)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue ADSCs cultured to passage PRP obtained from donor human patient	Mice (n=24) each transplanted with an average of 14.5 human follicular units (FU). Grafted post-radiation to transplanted areas Interventions: 1.ADSCs/PRP; 2.ADSCs; 3.PR Control: saline-injection	10Gy single exposure	Histology (H&E) IHC (Ki-67, Bcl-2, B-catenin) Western blotting (Bcl-2, Bax)	56 days post-radiation	Reduced atrophy, fibrosis, and skin keratinization in the ADSC-treated groups Highest proliferation (Ki-67), anti-apoptosis (Bcl-2), differentiation and signalling (beta-catenin) seen in FUs and skin of ADSCs/ PRP group, followed by ADSC-only and then PRP-only groups	ADSCs promote hair follicle regeneration, showing further potential for alleviating RIF (e.g., alopecia) and improving cosmetic outcomes PRP does not regenerate cells but may complement ADSC effects by providing a fibrin scaffold for repair
Yu et al. (2021)	Collagenase digestion, filtration and centrifugation of human adipose tissue SVC obtained	Rats (n=unknown) grafted post-radiation Intervention: SVF cell suspension Control: PBS-injection	45Gy single exposure	Clinical score (pathological signs) Histology (H&E) IHC (IL-6 and TGF-β1)	72 days post-radiation	SVF-treated skin showed intact epidermal covering and less inflammatory infiltration compared to control Reduced IL-6 and increased TGF-β1 in SVF-treated skin tissues	SVF attenuated RIF through anti-inflammatory mechanisms

Appendix table 4: Human Primers and Primer sequences for RT-qPCR from IDTTM.

Human qPCR Primer Pair Gene	Forward sequence	Reverse Sequence
<i>COL1A1</i>	GATTCCCTGGACCTAAAGGTGC	AGCCTCTCCATCTTTGCCAGCA
<i>TGFB1</i>	TACCTGAACCCGTGTTGCTCTC	GTTGCTGAGGTATCGCCAGGAA
<i>ACTA2</i>	CTATGCCTCTGGACGCACAACCT	CAGATCCAGACGCATGATGGCA
<i>MMP1</i>	ATGAAGCAGCCCAGATGTGGAG	TGGTCCACATCTGCTCTTGGCA
<i>MMP9</i>	GCCACTACTGTGCCTTTGAGTC	CCCTCAGAGAATCGCCAGTACT
<i>CCL19</i>	CGTGAGGAACTTCCACTACCTTC	GTCTCTGGATGATGCGTTCTACC
<i>TNC</i>	ATGTCCTCCTGACAGCCGAGAA	AGTCACGGTGAGGTTTTCCAGC
<i>CDKN1A</i>	AGGTGGACCTGGAGACTCTCAG	TCCTCTTGGAGAAGATCAGCCG
<i>CDKN1A</i>	CTCGTGCTGATGCTACTGAGGA	GGTCGGCGCAGTTGGGCTCC

Appendix Figure 1: In vitro findings of normal and chronic RIF fibroblast and ADSC co-culture experiments for the molecular targets of this study. (n=3)

Flow Cytometry Analysis

Appendix Figure 2: Flow cytometry gating strategy for the cell population.

Of the 60,000 events analyzed, 87.0% (52,191 cells) were identified as cells, rather than debris or noise. Among these, 77.5% were single cells (40,430 cells), indicating a successful effort to avoid cell clumping. Moreover, 89.3% of these single cells were viable (36,119 cells), underscoring the effectiveness of our cell preservation and revival methods.

The gating strategy began by excluding cell debris, duplets, and dead cells from the samples. Next, live single cells were further categorized based on their expression of different CD markers. The majority (99.7%) of live single cells were negative for hematopoietic markers CD45 and CD31, and positive (99.8%) for stromal markers CD90 and CD73, both of which are commonly found on mesenchymal stem cells including ADSCs.¹⁵⁰

Interestingly, of the cells that were CD45- CD31- CD90+ CD73+, 65.7% were positive for both CD34 and CD105 and an additional 6.47% were positive for CD105 but negative for CD34. This is noteworthy because while CD34 is a known marker for ADSCs, its expression can decrease with in vitro culture (its expression can be unstable), often leading to an increase in CD105 expression.¹⁵¹

Our data suggests that a significant proportion of our ADSCs retain both markers, suggesting a possible population of early progenitor or stem cells.

To provide a clearer visual representation of these results, the cells were categorized into quadrants based on their expression of CD34 and CD105. Quadrant 1 contained CD34- CD105+ cells (5.81% or 2,087 cells), Quadrant 2 contained CD34+ CD105+ cells (65.7% or 23,590 cells), Quadrant 3 contained CD34+ CD105- cells (21.0% or 7,550 cells), and Quadrant 4 contained CD34- CD105- cells (7.53% or 2,704 cells). This suggests a high degree of multipotency among these cells, as CD90 and CD73 are markers associated with mesenchymal stem cells.